

Advancing Computer-Aided Synthesis Planning: Prediction of Organic Reaction Outcomes using Transformer Models

Master's thesis

Franziska Weißbach

390492

29. Februar 2024

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN

FAKULTÄT II: MATHEMATIK UND NATURWISSENSCHAFTEN

FACHGEBIET TECHNISCHE CHEMIE

SUPERVISORS: PROF. DR. REINHARD SCHOMÄCKER

PROF. DR. FRANZISKA HESS

Thesis declaration

I hereby declare, that the present work: *Advancing Computer-Aided Synthesis Planning: Prediction of Organic Reaction Outcomes Using Transformer Models* is my own, unaided work and that all sources of information and references being used are listed to the best of my knowledge.

Die selbständige und eigenhändige Ausfertigung der vorliegenden Arbeit: *Advancing Computer-Aided Synthesis Planning: Prediction of Organic Reaction Outcomes Using Transformer Models* unter Verwendung ausschließlich der angegebenen Hilfsmittel und Quellen versichere ich an Eides statt.

Berlin, den 29. Februar 2024

(Franziska Weißbach)

Abstract

The present work investigates the application of forward reaction prediction in computer-aided synthesis planning (CASP), leveraging the BART transformer model and a large proprietary dataset from Reaxys, to enhance the design of synthesis routes. It demonstrates the model's capability to replicate established results from the literature on the predominantly used USPTO dataset but also reveals significant performance discrepancies when applied to the proprietary data. This highlights the limitations of current training datasets and the necessity for chemical data to be reported in a consistent form. The findings indicate that while increased data availability improves prediction performance, there exists a threshold beyond which additional data does not yield significant benefits for the specific model used. Furthermore, the impact of pretraining tasks is explored, showing that a combination of masked language modelling and prediction of physicochemical descriptors enhances model performance, especially in data-scarce scenarios. A varying accuracy of the model's predictions across different reaction types is observed and linked to the inconsistent representation of reactants, reagents and reaction conditions in the data. The model performs well in validating challenging synthesis steps and is able to provide insights into possible side reactions, thereby presenting itself as a valuable tool complementing the capabilities of other models in the field of CASP. However, limitations such as the quality of training data and the neglect of stereochemistry are identified, suggesting opportunities for future research. Moreover, exploring larger models and especially integrating reaction conditions and yields into predictions present promising approaches to improve forward prediction modelling. This work sets a foundation for improving forward reaction prediction models, emphasising their potential to aid synthetic chemistry through route validation and byproduct anticipation.

Zusammenfassung

Die vorliegende Arbeit untersucht die Anwendung der Reaktionsausgangsvorhersage in der computergestützten Synthesepipeline (CASP) und nutzt dabei das BART-Transformermodell und einen großen proprietären Datensatz von Reaxys, um das Design von Syntheserouten zu verbessern. Das Modell ist in der Lage etablierte Ergebnisse aus der Literatur zum überwiegend verwendeten USPTO-Datensatz zu reproduzieren, zeigt aber auch erhebliche Leistungsunterschiede bei der Anwendung auf die proprietären Daten auf. Dies verdeutlicht die Grenzen aktueller Trainingsdatensätze und die Notwendigkeit, chemische Daten in konsistenter Form zu publizieren. Die Ergebnisse deuten darauf hin, dass eine erhöhte Datenverfügbarkeit zwar die Vorhersageleistung verbessert, es jedoch einen Schwellenwert gibt, ab dem zusätzliche Daten keine signifikanten Vorteile für das spezifische verwendete Modell bringen. Darüber hinaus werden die Auswirkungen von Transfer Learning untersucht und gezeigt, dass eine Kombination aus Masked Language Modeling und der Vorhersage physikalisch-chemischer Deskriptoren die Modellleistung verbessert, insbesondere in datenarmen Szenarien. Es fällt auf, dass die Vorhersagen des Modells über verschiedene Reaktionstypen hinweg sehr unterschiedlich genau sind und dies mit der inkonsistenten Darstellung von Reaktanden, Reagenzien und Reaktionsbedingungen in den Daten zusammenhängt. Das Modell eignet sich gut für die Validierung anspruchsvoller Syntheseschritte und ist in der Lage, Einblicke in mögliche Nebenreaktionen zu liefern, wodurch es sich als wertvolles Werkzeug erweist, das die Fähigkeiten anderer Modelle im Bereich CASP ergänzen kann. Es sind jedoch Schwächen zu erkennen wie die Abhängigkeit der Ergebnisse von der Qualität der Trainingsdaten und die Vernachlässigung der Stereochemie, die in zukünftigen Forschungsvorhaben beachtet werden sollten. Darüber hinaus stellen die Erforschung größerer Modelle und insbesondere die Integration von Reaktionsbedingungen und -ausbeuten in Vorhersagen vielversprechende Ansätze zur Verbesserung der Modellierung für Reaktionsausgangsvorhersage dar. Diese Arbeit legt wichtige Grundlagen für die Verbesserung von Modellen zur Vorhersage von Reaktionsausgängen und betont deren Potenzial, die Synthesechemie durch Routenvalidierung und Antizipieren von Nebenprodukten zu unterstützen.

Contents

List of figures	vii
List of tables	viii
1 Introduction	1
2 Theoretical Background	3
2.1 Introduction to Deep Learning	3
2.1.1 Artificial neurons	3
2.1.2 Loss functions	4
2.1.3 Gradient descent and backpropagation of error	5
2.2 Transformers in Natural Language Processing	6
2.3 An Overview of Computer-Aided Synthesis Planning (CASP)	8
2.3.1 SMILES notation	9
2.3.2 Chemical reaction data	10
2.3.3 Data augmentation	11
2.3.4 Sequence-to-Sequence Forward Reaction Prediction	11
2.4 Transfer Learning	13
3 Methodology	15
3.1 Model architecture and Hyperparameters	15
3.1.1 Implementation details	17
3.1.2 Tokenisation and vocabulary	17
3.2 Data sources	18
3.3 Data preprocessing	19
3.4 Training and validation	21
3.4.1 Batching	22
3.4.2 Pretraining	23
3.4.3 Finetuning	23
3.4.4 Evaluation	23
4 Results	25
4.1 Baseline experiments	25
4.1.1 Model variance	26
4.2 Influence of training set size	26
4.3 Differences between Data Sources	28
4.4 Effects of Pretraining	30
4.4.1 Baseline: no pretraining	31

4.4.2	Masked Language Modelling	32
4.4.3	Prediction of Molecular Descriptors	34
4.4.4	Influence of Finetuning Dataset Size	36
4.5	Evaluation of model performance	38
4.5.1	Example reactions relevant to retrosynthesis	42
4.5.2	Uncertainty estimation for predictions	44
4.6	Prediction of reaction byproducts and side products	45
4.6.1	Examples from textbooks and the literature	46
4.6.2	Reactions extracted from US patents with given byproducts	48
4.6.3	Reaction class specific predictions	48
4.6.4	Training on reactions with multiple reported products	52
5	Conclusion and Outlook	55
A	Appendix	I

List of Figures

2.1	Conceptual visualisation of a single artificial neuron	4
2.2	A dense neural net with two hidden layers, m inputs and p outputs.	4
2.3	Architecture of the transformer model	7
2.4	Molecular structure of acetylsalicylic acid and multiple valid SMILES representations.	10
3.1	Training procedures for pretraining on chemical structures and forward reaction prediction finetuning.	16
3.2	Distribution of the top-level reaction classes in the Reaxys reaction dataset.	22
4.1	Development of training and validation loss and validation molecular accuracy over the course of the model training on USPTO data according to Irwin et al. [52]’s methods.	26
4.2	Top-1 accuracy of a randomly initialised model over the size of the dataset it was trained on.	27
4.3	Mean prediction accuracy of the best pretrained Chemformer model [52] on the test set of the Reaxys reaction data.	29
4.4	Molecular and token accuracies on the validation set over the number of training steps for a randomly initialised model trained on five million reactions from Reaxys.	31
4.5	Molecular accuracy on the validation set over the course of the finetuning process after 50 thousand and eight million steps MLM pretraining.	33
4.6	Molecular accuracy over the course of the finetuning process after pre-training using only MLM and MLM in combination with physicochemical descriptor prediction.	35
4.7	Difference in top-1 accuracy between pretrained and randomly initialised models for training/finetuning on datasets of different sizes.	37
4.8	Mean top-1, top-2 and top-3 molecular prediction accuracies per reaction class on the test dataset.	38
4.9	Top-1 accuracies of the finer granulated reaction classes plotted over their frequency in the dataset.	39
4.10	A nitration reaction from the Reaxys database and the top 3 predictions of the product.	40
4.11	Top-1 accuracy over the average number of given reactants aggregated over the different individual reaction classes. The marker colour indicates the density of markers in that position and the area of the markers indicates the number of reactions in the respective class.	41
4.12	A correctly predicted Ugi reaction with the second most likely prediction being a possible side product of the Passerini reaction.	43

4.13	A reaction proposed during retrosynthesis route search, which is not experimentally feasible and the predictions of the forward reaction model for the given reactants.	44
4.14	Relationship between Likelihood of a sampled prediction and its Tanimoto similarity coefficient to the target product.	45
4.15	An electrophilic addition reaction from [94] yielding a recorded major product and a minor product according to Markovnikov's rule.	46
4.16	Grignard reaction for the mono-alkylation of dichlorobenzene.	47
4.17	Reaction of a cyclical ketone containing an alkene group with a peroxy acid.	47
4.18	Top-1, top-2 and top-3 mean prediction accuracies on the test set for the prediction with lowest level NameRxn reaction class information as additional input accumulated over the highest level NameRxn classes.	49
4.19	Top-1 accuracy of the model trained with indication of the NameRxn assigned reaction class over the average number of given reactants aggregated over the different individual reaction classes.	50
4.20	Predictions for the nitration reaction shown in Figure 4.10, when the model input is supplemented with the token representing nitration.	50
4.21	Predictions for the combined Prilezhaev and Baeyer-Villiger oxidation reaction from [96] (see Figure 4.17), when specific tokens representing the reaction types (top row: Prilezhaev, bottom row: Baeyer-Villiger) are added to the model input.	51
4.22	Predicted reaction products for the two reactants proposed in Figure 4.13 with reaction class specified in model input. Top: Ether halide coupling specified, Bottom: Amide Schotten-Baumann specified	52
A.1	A reaction from Reaxys, that is categorised as purification by NextMove. The SMILES strings for reactant and product are not identical, because the SMILES notation is not able to represent the aromaticity [99].	I
A.2	Finetuning behaviour of models pretrained for 50 thousand, 6 million and 8 million steps on the MLM pretraining task. Finetuning on 5 million reactions.	II
A.3	Finetuning on five million reactions for models pretrained with two different sequence representation strategies for descriptor prediction. Randomly initialised model for comparison.	II
A.4	A reaction from Bruice [94], where two products are produced in equal measure. Target 1 is predicted with a Likelihood of 0.23 and Target 2 with a Likelihood of 0.05.	III

List of Tables

3.1	Hyperparameters of the BART model	17
3.2	Summary of top-level reaction categories taken from the Reaxys dataset.	21
4.1	Top-1 molecular accuracy for the pretrained models finetuned on datasets of different sizes and the random initialised models for comparison. . .	37

List of Symbols

Symbol	Meaning	Unit
Latin characters		
d	Number of dimensions	-
E	Model dimensionality	-
g	Activation function	-
H	Cross-entropy	-
K	Key matrix	-
L	Loss	-
N	Batch size	-
p	Probability	-
Q	Query matrix	-
S	Source sequence length	-
V	Value matrix	-
w	Weight	-
x	Model input	-
\hat{y}	Model output	-
z	Hidden layer nodes	-
Greek characters		
η	Learning rate	-
Abbreviations		
AI	Artificial intelligence	
ANN	Artificial neural network	
BOS	Begin of sequence	
CASP	Computer-aided synthesis planning	
ML	Machine learning	
MLM	Masked language modelling	
MSE	Mean squared error	
NLP	Natural language processing	
ReLU	Rectified linear unit	
SDPA	Scaled dot-product attention	
SMILES	Simplified molecular input line entry system	
TPSA	Topological polar surface area	
USPTO	United States patent and trademark office	

1 Introduction

The design of synthesis routes is a crucial problem in chemistry due to its profound impact on scientific innovation, drug development, and industrial applications. Crafting efficient and reliable synthetic pathways enables access to new molecules, materials, and compounds that could have essential pharmaceutical, agricultural, or industrial uses. Moreover, optimising synthesis routes contributes to sustainability efforts by reducing waste, energy consumption, and overall costs associated with chemical production, making it a pivotal concern in modern chemistry.

Computer-aided synthesis planning (CASP) has been around since the 1960s [1], created with the aim to assist chemists in their task of designing efficient routes for the synthesis of target compounds from available starting materials [2]. Since then, the field has come a long way, adopting new developments in the area of machine learning to its advantage [3] and developing a collection of powerful tools, which are able to generate complete synthesis routes and consider user specifications such as diversity or availability of starting materials [4, 5].

Next to retrosynthesis, the prediction of reaction outcomes, termed forward prediction to distinguish the two, has found an important application in CASP for the validation of reactions that are proposed by retrosynthesis tools [6]. Successful forward prediction is able to increase the quality of generated synthesis routes and decrease the experimental effort for the development of new routes. It is also used to predict reactivity in various contexts, metabolic pathways, drug formulation or stability being just a few examples [7]. The aim of the present work is to train forward reaction prediction models and evaluate their performance for the use in validating retrosynthesis pathways and predicting side products and byproducts for a given reaction.

There exists a broad range of approaches to modelling chemical reactivity from quantum chemical ab-initio calculations on one end of the spectrum to general reactivity models based on data-driven modelling methods on the other end [8]. Quantum-mechanical methods for modelling and predicting chemical reactivity rely on hypotheses and do not require large amounts of empirical data, however they are computationally expensive and have notable limitations regarding the complexity of systems. A growing amount of publicly available data [9] and progress in the field of Machine Learning (ML) and especially Artificial Intelligence (AI) have lowered the barrier to entry for data-driven reactivity modelling. It is promising an alternative, though fundamentally different, approach to quantum chemical modelling methods. Such ML methods take considerable resources in the form of data and compute power to train but are comparatively fast in

their application for predicting unseen reactions [10].

The models developed in this work fall into the category of data-driven general reactivity models and are based on the transformer model [11], an architecture of artificial neural networks, that was originally developed for use in machine translation. Their state-of-the-art performance in natural language processing (NLP) has led to them being used in various different application areas [12].

As the access to high-quality reaction data is limited, strategies like transfer learning are used to develop general-purpose abilities and knowledge on a data-rich task that can be transferred to downstream tasks [13]. This work leverages a large proprietary reaction dataset to critically explore the impact of transfer learning on forward reaction prediction, generating insights into the effectiveness of the approach.

The theoretical background chapter will give an overview over the machine learning concepts used in this work and present the literature on data-driven forward reaction prediction. In the following chapter, the methodology for data processing and modelling will be described. Chapter four will present the results of this thesis, beginning with a comparison to models and data from the literature. Thereafter, the effectiveness of transfer learning will be discussed, followed by an in-depth evaluation of the models' capabilities with a focus on their application to validate synthesis pathways and predict side products. The thesis closes with a summary and a look into future research possibilities.

2 Theoretical Background

The Transformer Model has in recent years obtained the status of state-of-the-art model architecture in Natural Language Processing[12]. Since its introduction in 2017 by Vaswani et al. [11] for machine translation tasks it has also been successfully applied to research questions in other fields such as computer vision [14] or genomic sequence analysis [15]. To be able to discuss the application of transformer models to computer-aided synthesis planning (CASP), it is necessary to first gain an understanding of the fundamental principles of deep learning and the transformer model architecture, which will be presented briefly in the following. Furthermore, an overview of the developments in CASP and more specifically forward reaction prediction will be given as well as introductions to the line notation for molecules SMILES and the concept of transfer learning.

2.1 Introduction to Deep Learning

Deep Learning is a class of machine learning methods able to extract patterns from data using artificial neural networks (ANNs). Conventional machine learning often depends on domain experts hand engineering a set of features from the raw data, that the learning algorithm then can use to make decisions [16]. This process poses a strong limitation for these techniques as it is time consuming and not scalable in practice. The idea behind deep learning is to enable the machine to be fed with raw data and automatically discover the representations needed for its task, yet in practice the selection of inputs significantly influences outcomes [17]. Multiple layers of artificial neurons are used to progressively extract higher-level features from the raw input. This structure is inspired by the network of neurons in human and animal brains. However, there are substantial differences between the two and the learning process is based on conventional mathematical optimisation.

2.1.1 Artificial neurons

The most basic building block of a neural network is a single artificial neuron, also called a node. It is a mathematical function, which takes multiple inputs $x_1 \dots x_m$ (the feature vector) and produces one output \hat{y} and can be written as such:

$$\hat{y} = g \left(w_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m x_i w_i \right). \quad (2.1)$$

$w_1 \dots w_m$ denote the weights that are assigned to each input and w_0 represents the bias of this artificial neuron. A (piecewise) non-linear activation function g is applied to the output of the neuron to introduce non-linearities into the network, that enable it to deal with non-linear data. Figure 2.1 shows a conceptual visualisation of an artificial neuron.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual visualisation of a single artificial neuron

A neural network consists of many interconnected neurons, that are usually arranged into layers. Each neuron in a layer takes the same inputs, computes the activation function of the sum of the weighted inputs and passes the result on as one input to the next layer of neurons. Layers positioned between the input and output layer are called hidden layers. An example network is shown in Figure 2.2. During the training process,

Figure 2.2: A dense neural net with two hidden layers, m inputs and p outputs.

the weights $w_i(n, m)$ and biases $w_0(n, m)$ of a neural network are optimised using in most cases the stochastic gradient descent algorithm [18].

2.1.2 Loss functions

For the optimisation of the network weights an objective function is necessary, which is usually called the loss function. The value of the loss function depending on the network weights and a given set of input(s) and target(s) is termed the loss. Its purpose is to give a good measure of the performance of the neural network on the given training

task. For real-valued predictions, in the case of regression, it is common to use the squared error $(y - \hat{y})^2$ as the loss function, while for discrete-valued predictions, found in classification tasks, the use of softmax cross-entropy is common and has proven successful for many applications [18]. However, other loss functions in frequent use exist. In the case of the cross-entropy loss function for classification, the *softmax function* is used to convert a vector of K real-valued outputs into a probability distribution of K possible outcomes. The softmax function is also known as the normalised exponential function and its output can be used to represent categorical distributions. The cross-entropy loss measures the difference between the known target probability distribution P for the labels in a multi-class classification task X and the predicted probability distribution Q [19].

$$H(P, Q) = - \sum_{x \in X} p(x) \log q(x) \quad (2.2)$$

2.1.3 Gradient descent and backpropagation of error

Gradient descent is the most commonly used method to optimise the weights of an ANN in respect to the loss function and was also employed in this work. Here the weights are initialised randomly and then the gradient of the loss function $\frac{\partial L(W)}{\partial W}$ is computed to determine the necessary changes in the weights to improve performance of the ANN. This calculation is done using the backpropagation algorithm. It involves the flow of error signals through feedback connections from the output of the network towards the input via the chain rule [20].

Since the datasets used for deep learning are usually very large, it is not computationally efficient to compute the mentioned gradient $\frac{\partial L(W)}{\partial W}$ for all observations in the training data. Instead, the data is divided into batches of a certain size. The gradient is then computed for the observations of one batch at a time and used to update the weights. This practice is a stochastic approximation of gradient descent optimisation and is known as stochastic gradient descent. The weights are then updated by taking a step in the direction of the negative computed gradient.

$$W_i = W_{i-1} - \eta \frac{\partial L(W_{i-1})}{\partial W} \quad (2.3)$$

The η denotes the learning-rate, a hyperparameter that is adjusted during the training. Here, the Adam optimiser [21], a variation of the stochastic gradient descent algorithm, is used, where a learning rate per parameter is calculated. Another influential hyperparameter is the batch-size. With its choice a compromise has to be made. The larger the batch-size, the more effort it takes to compute the gradient, but the smaller the

batch-size, the more stochastic is the resulting estimate of the gradient. Batching of the data leads to faster training compared to true (non-stochastic) gradient descent, in part because it allows for parallel computation of batches. Both learning rate and batch-size have a strong influence on the generalisation ability of an ANN and its convergence behaviour [22].

Deep learning has proven to be highly effective in uncovering complex patterns within high dimensional data, therefore enabling application in a wide range of fields such as science, business, and media [16]. Its ability to take advantage of the increasing amount of digitally available data and compute power has launched its ongoing wave of successes [23, 18].

2.2 Transformers in Natural Language Processing

The term transformer usually describes a specific architecture of deep neural networks, that relies on the parallel multi-head attention mechanism [11]. Like recurrent neural network architectures, which were considered to be state-of-the-art before its emergence, it is able to process sequential data and solve sequence-to-sequence transduction problems. However, it is much faster to train, because it forgoes the recurrence component of previous models in favour of the attention mechanism to model dependencies between input and output sequences, allowing for significant parallelisation.

To use transformer models on sequences of text, a numerical representation of language is needed. First, input text is split into shorter substrings, which are encoded as categorical variables (tokens). In Natural Language Processing (NLP) these substrings can be for example individual ASCII characters, syllables, whole words or combinations of words or even short sentences. Embeddings map these discrete variables to a vector of fixed size. They aim to reduce the dimensionality of categorical variables and provide a meaningful representation in the vector space. This is often done by training a neural network to generate learned embeddings [24]. Information about the position of tokens in the sequence is added to the input embeddings in the form of positional encodings [11].

The transformer as originally published [11] possesses an *encoder-decoder* structure. The task of the encoder is to map an input sequence of embeddings to a sequence of continuous representations, which is then used by the decoder to autoregressively generate an output sequence of tokens. To generate this output sequence the decoder predicts the probability distribution over all tokens in the model's vocabulary at each position in the output sequence based on the input and the preceding tokens in the

sequence. To do this the target sequence is tokenised, embedded and added to positional encodings as well and then shifted one token to the right, before being passed into the decoder. This right shift is done so that for every position i in the target sequence the decoder has access to the source sequence and all positions in the target sequence $0 \dots i - 1$ that have been produced so far, but not the target token for position i . The probability distributions over all tokens, which are produced by the decoder are compared to the true target distribution of probability 1 for the observed token and 0 for all other tokens in the vocabulary by using a cross-entropy loss function.

The predicted probability distributions yield a search graph of possible tokens and their respective predicted probabilities from which a sequence has to be extracted. For this task the heuristic beam search strategy is often used, which explores the graph breadth-first and only stores a predetermined number of best states for expansion [25]. This way multiple sequences are obtained, which are assigned their overall likelihoods.

Both encoder and decoder are composed of a series of identical layers. The layers in the encoder stack each consist of two sub-layers, a self-attention layer and a dense feed-forward network. For the decoder stack a third sub-layer is added, which performs attention over the output of the encoder stack and a mask is applied to the self-attention sub-layer enforcing the autoregressive processing of the output sequence. A schematic of the architecture is shown in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Architecture of the transformer model [11]. The left block depicts the encoder part, the right block the decoder.

The attention mechanism enables the model to identify and attend to the most important tokens. It computes attention scores, which determine how much each token in the sequence should contribute to the other tokens’ representations [26]. It is essentially a function that creates three vectors labelled query, key and value from an input vector and maps them to an output vector [27]. The query, key and value vectors are calculated by multiplying the input vector by the weight matrices W^Q , W^K , W^V respectively. These matrices are learned during training [27]. The computation of the attention presented in Vaswani et al. [11] is done by calculating the dot products of the query with all keys, multiplying each by the scaling factor $\frac{1}{d_k}$ and applying a softmax function before calculating the weighted sum over the respective value vectors. For efficiency these steps are done in the form of matrix multiplication by combining a set of queries, keys and values into the matrices Q , K and V respectively.

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (2.4)$$

This type of attention is referred to as Scaled Dot-Product Attention (SDPA) and commonly used in transformer models. Multiple parallel attention layers can help the model focus on different positions in the form of multi-head attention. Multiple sets of query, key and value matrices are randomly initialised and learn to project into different representation subspaces [27].

While originally developed for NLP applications, the transformer architecture has since found its way into countless other application areas, such as speech recognition [28], protein structure prediction [29] computer-aided synthesis planning (CASP) [30] and many more.

2.3 An Overview of Computer-Aided Synthesis Planning (CASP)

Software for computer-aided synthesis planning aims to accelerate the design of synthesis routes for chemical compounds [2]. Ideally, such a software tool would be able to identify possible reaction schemes for the synthesis of a specified target molecule and provide chemists with detailed descriptions including information on reaction conditions, yields and side products.

In the 1960s Corey [31] introduced his technique of retrosynthetic analysis for recursively choosing suitable disconnections in a target molecule. Soon after, the first CASP tools were developed, which relied on a manually constructed chemical knowledge base [32, 1]. A prominent expert-AI computer program that still pursues this approach of expert-coded reaction rules is Chematica (now available as Synthia) [33]. It operates on

more than a hundred thousand reaction rules that were compiled over the span of 20 years [34]. Its successes notwithstanding [33], this approach is thought by many to be at a disadvantage in comparison to the data-driven algorithms that have been flourishing in recent years thanks to the advances in machine learning [35]. It is prone to human error and bias, brittle and not as scalable [1]. Data-driven models have evolved from statistical models and rely on data to establish relationships between input, internal and output variables without detailed knowledge of underlying processes [36]. The deep learning models developed in this work follow this paradigm.

Several types of such mathematical ML models have been developed, that learn from large sets of reaction data and are capable of retrosynthetic analysis and/or prediction of reaction outcomes (also called forward reaction prediction). They can be grouped into three different strategies. One approach is to extract reaction rules and templates automatically from reaction examples and apply the resulting template library to a target to generate precursors [2]. Another is to render molecules as graphs and train graph neural networks to predict bond changes in the reactants [37]. Finally, sequence-to-sequence models inspired by neural machine translation advancements are applied to generate product or precursor molecules [38, 1]. The latter is the strategy that is implemented in this work. These sequence-to-sequence models use the SMILES (simplified molecular-input line-entry system, see 2.3.1 below) to represent chemical structures in text format. With this, the reaction prediction task can be thought of as a translation task, translating from a set of reactants to the corresponding product(s) or vice versa.

2.3.1 SMILES notation

The simplified molecular-input line-entry system is a line notation used to express the structure of molecules in the form of a string of ASCII characters. Created in 1986 the SMILES notation has since gained popularity and the open standard OpenSMILES was developed in 2007 [39]. Its description of chemical structures is amenable to algorithmic interpretation and has been significant in the advance of molecular machine learning [10]. Because the SMILES notation follows a grammar not unlike that of a natural language, it is readily used with methods from NLP. Its rules do not guarantee every character combination to correspond to a chemical structure, therefore it is possible to generate invalid SMILES strings.

Atoms are represented by their standard abbreviation in the periodic table and are assumed to be connected by a single bond to neighbouring atoms unless specified otherwise. A SMILES string can be obtained by traversing the graph representation of a

compound depth-first, removing hydrogen atoms and breaking cycles. By choosing a different starting atom for the traversal or traversing branches in a different order the resulting SMILES string can be modified. Figure 2.4 shows the molecular structure of acetylsalicylic acid and three different valid SMILES strings to describe it.

Figure 2.4: Molecular structure of acetylsalicylic acid and multiple valid SMILES representations.

It has the advantage that it is both human-readable and human-writable, but is not without drawbacks. Perhaps its greatest limitation is the fact that multiple equally valid SMILES strings can exist for one molecule but that there is no unified way to generate a canonical representation [40].

2.3.2 Chemical reaction data

Availability of chemical reaction data is limited. There are large reaction corpora, like Reaxys [41] or CAS reactions [42], however they are proprietary and not accessible to the general public. The largest open-access reaction data set was extracted from the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) database in 2016 [9] and is commonly referred to as the USPTO data set. It contains around 1.3 million unique chemical reactions, which are given amongst others in the form of reaction SMILES and with additional information such as yields and descriptions of the procedure if available. It suffers from a number of shortcomings, as it contains systematic extraction errors and partly incomplete reactions and the atom-mapping from reactants to products is not reliable [1]. Atom-mapping can pose problems, when incomplete, unbalanced reactions are published and it can make no claim to the true reaction mechanism [32]. The open reaction database [43] aims to combat these problems by providing an open-access infrastructure for structuring and sharing organic reaction data in a consistent format.

2.3.3 Data augmentation

Data augmentation refers to strategies aiming to increase the diversity of training examples without explicitly collecting new data [44]. To do this, slightly modified copies of existing data are added to the training set. While these strategies are especially widespread in the field of computer-vision where approaches like continuous noising can be used, their use in NLP is relatively underexplored, likely due to the discrete nature of language data [44].

However, the SMILES notation lends itself naturally to a form of data augmentation, where different valid SMILES representations for the same molecule are randomly generated. This is termed SMILES augmentation and has been used in machine learning models e.g. to decrease overfitting [45].

2.3.4 Sequence-to-Sequence Forward Reaction Prediction

Forward reaction prediction is the prediction of the products of a chemical reaction given a set of reactants and conditions [32]. It is closely related to retrosynthesis and the same techniques are employed. An important use-case is the validation of retrosynthesis steps in CASP tools [1]. Methods for the validation of reaction steps already exist, such as deep ANN binary classifiers to predict whether a reaction is feasible [46, 47]. They are much faster than the generation of the product SMILES using a sequence-to-sequence model could be and are trained on positive as well as negative reaction data, which gives them an important advantage over models trained only on positive data [48]. However, these binary feasibility classifiers have weaknesses due to limitations and biases in the training data that could be compensated by the abilities of a sequence-to-sequence model, which could be hypothesised to learn more generalisable patterns in organic chemistry.

Different model architectures that were originally developed for translating between natural languages have been employed in the sequence-based approach to forward reaction prediction, the first being a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) proposed by Nam and Kim [49]. In recent years the transformer architecture has established itself as state-of-the-art for reaction prediction models leveraging its ability to capture long-range dependencies in sequences [34]. It takes as input the SMILES representation of the reactants and reagents and generates SMILES strings for possible reaction products, which are ranked according to their calculated likelihood (see section 2.2). These calculated likelihoods have been shown to provide an accurate uncertainty estimation [30] and could potentially give insights into the generation of side products.

The input SMILES strings are tokenised and then embedded to obtain a numerical representation (see 2.2). To break down the strings into series of tokens a typical strategy is character-wise tokenisation, also called atom-wise tokenisation. With atom-wise tokenisation each token corresponds to one atom (hydrogen implicit), bond or other ASCII character denoting the molecule structure. This can be criticised for not reflecting the influence of an atom’s surroundings on its characteristics [50]. Small, common molecules are sometimes represented as a single token. Some models separate the input molecules into reactants and reagents, while others do not differentiate between the two. It can be argued, that this separation is not helpful for the prediction, because there is no clear definition to distinguish between reactants and reagents and the differentiation can only be reliably made if the product(s) of the reaction are already known. Therefore, this practice could lead to data leakage and impair the prediction capabilities at inference time [34].

The amount of reaction data for which reliable information on reaction conditions is readily available is very small and a consistent way to encode this information to be used by neural networks in reaction prediction has not yet been widely adopted. This is why most data-driven models for reaction prediction have not incorporated any information regarding reaction conditions into their training [1]. However, a number of research groups have developed machine learning models that are able to suggest reaction conditions for a given reaction [34]. Other important aspects of reactivity prediction such as yields, kinetics or proportion of side and byproducts can also not be incorporated at the moment but are targeted with individual approaches [35, 51]

The first transformer model capable of forward reaction prediction to be published was the Molecular Transformer by Schwaller et al. [30] in 2019. It outperformed all algorithms in the literature at that time and achieved a top-1 accuracy of 88.6 % on the USPTO-MIT benchmark set [37] with mixed reactants and reagents and SMILES augmentation. Tetko et al. [45] conducted a study of different SMILES augmentation schemes and reported an improved top-1 accuracy on the USPTO-MIT mixed dataset, when augmenting both input and target data. Irwin et al. [52] later published their Chemformer model, which served as the basis for the models developed in this work. They report a top-1 accuracy of over 90% on the mixed USPTO-MIT dataset. However, the Chemformer model suffers of a reduced diversity of the top-n predictions, where the n sampled SMILES strings with the highest likelihoods are mainly equivalent representations of the same molecule. This is presumably caused by their SMILES augmentation scheme. The chemformer uses self-supervised pretraining to improve the performance and speed up convergence. Pretraining involves initialising the model’s weights by exposing it to a large amount of data in the form of transfer learning.

2.4 Transfer Learning

Transfer learning is a technique in machine learning, which is based on the aim to use knowledge that a model gained from training on one task in the training of a different, but related, task. It is often applied by using a large, more general dataset to pretrain a model and then training the model further on a more specific task with a usually smaller dataset in what is called a finetuning step [53, 18].

With the Chemformer model, Irwin et al. [52] introduced the idea of a foundation model for chemistry with SMILES as its language. The goal is to reduce the computational effort by training a multi purpose model that can be finetuned for many downstream tasks even with limited resources and thereby making the model more accessible for other users. They used a dataset of 100 million unlabelled molecules for pretraining and finetuned models for a number of different downstream tasks, such as forward reaction prediction, molecular optimisation and molecular property prediction. The pretraining is thought to teach the model a useful representation of molecules in the chemical space. Two pretraining tasks, masked language modelling (MLM) and SMILES augmentation, and their combination were investigated.

MLM has proven wildly successful as a pretraining technique in natural language processing [54] and has since been adapted to other domains. MLM is a form of self-supervised learning in that supervisory signals are generated from the data itself and no explicit input-label pairs are needed. Taking the tokenised SMILES string of a chemical structure, short subsequences are randomly replaced with a special token, denoted as <MASK>. The masked sequences serve as input for the encoder, while the target given to the decoder is the original unmasked token sequence, shifted to the right (see section 2.2).

With this pretraining task the model is supposed to learn from the inherent structure in molecules. While masked language modelling works well in natural language processing, it can be conjectured that the SMILES representation of a molecule lacks the necessary relationships between individual tokens in a sequence, quasi the equivalent context in a natural language phrase, for this method to be of much value.

SMILES augmentation can be used as a pretraining task by generating a non-canonical SMILES string representing the input molecule via random permutation of the atom order and giving it to the model as input. The model is then asked to predict the canonical form of the SMILES string, which is provided as the target sequence.

Ross et al. [55] explored the representational power of pretrained chemical language

models in predicting a broad range of downstream molecular properties. They used over 1.1 billion chemical structures from ZINC [56] and PubChem [57] for the MLM pretraining and claim that their model learned spatial relationships between atoms within a molecule and captures chemical and structural information. Another study of molecular representation learning with language models employed combinations of MLM, SMILES augmentation and prediction of real-valued molecular descriptors as pretraining tasks [58]. The molecular descriptors were calculated in RDKit [59] and the language model was trained to predict the descriptors for the molecules whose SMILES strings it was given. In this study the combination of MLM and the prediction of the molecular descriptors as a self-supervised pretraining task performed better than all other combinations of tasks and was able to improve a model's performance on downstream tasks. The prediction of molecular descriptors as a pretraining task is especially interesting, because it could function as the chemical context for the MLM pretraining mentioned earlier. The authors found that the addition of the SMILES augmentation pretraining task slightly but consistently decreases performance.

The pretraining methods discussed above have been shown to improve the performance of models for sequence-to-sequence, regression and classification downstream tasks, when the amount of data available for fine-tuning is very limited [52, 55, 58]. However, no research has been done on whether this effect also occurs, when the amount of data for fine-tuning is substantially larger. Wollenhaupt, Villalba, and Ravitz [47] also highlight the importance of the data's breadth, quality and consistency.

During the course of this work Westerlund et al. [60] published a study in which they trained a Chemformer model [52] for forward prediction on a large proprietary dataset of 18 million reactions. The model achieved a top-1 accuracy at around 64%. Unfortunately, forward prediction was not the focus of their work which is why they did not publish a more detailed evaluation of the forward prediction model.

The presented theoretical background and current research activities show that the aims for this present work to develop and evaluate transformer models for forward reaction prediction to be used in the validation of synthesis routes and prediction of side and byproducts are based on a strong foundation. The use of large, proprietary reaction datasets together with different pretraining methods promises to enable a thorough assessment of the models' capabilities. The next chapter will present the methods used to this effect.

3 Methodology

The following section details the methods and resources used in this work.

3.1 Model architecture and Hyperparameters

The Chemformer model by Irwin et al. [52] was used as a starting point for the experiments and adjusted for the use of newer python libraries and additional chemical data and pretraining tasks. The BART (Bidirectional and Auto-Regressive Transformers) [61] encoder-decoder architecture was adopted from the published code from the Chemformer architecture [52] in its smaller form which consists of 45 million trainable parameters to limit use of computational resources, instead of the larger model Chemformer-Large, which performed only marginally better. Detailed information about the size of the model and hyperparameter values can be found in Table 3.1. The hyperparameters were also adopted from Chemformer, where the authors performed hyperparameter tuning.

The training procedure for the forward reaction prediction task, which is used individually but also as the finetuning step of pretrained models, is visualised in Figure 3.1a. The reactants' SMILES string is tokenised (more on that in section 3.1.2), embedded into vectors and added to sinusoidal positional encodings [11], before it is passed on to the encoder layers of the transformer (see section 2.2). The representation that is output by the encoder is then input into the decoder layers. The SMILES string of the target product(s) is tokenised, embedded and added to positional encodings as well and then shifted one token to the right, before being passed into the decoder. Cross-entropy is used as a loss function.

Two different pretraining tasks are employed here. One is the masked language modelling (MLM) task as it was used for the Chemformer [52] and the other is the prediction of RDKit calculated molecule descriptors as it was presented by Fabian et al. [58]. While MLM has been used for pretraining of a forward prediction model before, the prediction of descriptors has not been examined in this context yet, which will be an important aspect of this work.

For the MLM pretraining task the span masking algorithm [62] is used to select the token positions to be masked. To combine MLM with the prediction of the molecular descriptors an additional regression head is incorporated into the model structure (see Figure 3.1b), which is composed of two fully connected feed-forward layers of the same

Figure 3.1: Training procedures for pretraining on chemical structures and forward reaction prediction finetuning. $\langle \text{BOS} \rangle$ stands for the begin of sequence token, $\langle \text{EOS} \rangle$ for the end of sequence token and $\langle \text{MASK} \rangle$ for the mask token.

dimension as the model. The regression head outputs the predictions for the eight descriptors and is trained with a Mean-Squared-Error (MSE) loss function. It takes a fixed-size representation of the SMILES fed into the encoder of shape (N, E) as input, with N being the number of sequences in a batch and E the model dimensionality, the number of expected features of the encoder and decoder inputs [63]. However, the output of the encoder is of shape (S, N, E) with S the source sequence length, therefore the dimension representing the individual tokens in the sequences has to be condensed into a fixed-size representation of the whole sequence [64]. This is often termed pooling.

A simple but useful method is mean or average pooling, where the representations for all tokens in a sequence are averaged to obtain a representation for the whole sequence. Another approach is to use the representation of the begin-of-sequence token (BOS), which is prepended to every sequence for the sequence as a whole. This token contains no information itself but can be imbued with information from all other tokens in the sequence by means of the calculated attentions [62]. Both of these representation strategies are used and compared in this work.

While Irwin et al. [52] applied SMILES augmentation during pretraining and finetuning in accordance with the findings of Schwaller et al. [30] and Tetko et al. [45], that augmentation boosts model performance by providing additional training data, they found that augmentation leads to a strong decrease in the number of unique predictions per reaction. The higher the fraction was of non-canonical SMILES used during training, the higher the fraction of non-canonical SMILES that describe the same molecule was in the predictions. Therefore, the observed improvement in the prediction with the highest likelihood caused by SMILES augmentation has to be weighed against the considerably larger decrease in new, correct predictions with lower likelihoods. Due

to the much larger size of the training dataset available for this work in comparison with the USPTO data and the negative effects of SMILES augmentation pretraining on finetuning observed by Fabian et al. [58], SMILES augmentation was not used in this work.

Table 3.1: Hyperparameters of the BART model

Parameter	Value
Model dimension	512
Feed-forward Layers	1024 6
Attention heads	8
Trainable parameters	$45 \cdot 10^6$
Activation function	RELU
Normalisation layout	pre-norm
Dropout	0.1

Random dropout is employed as an effective regularisation method to avoid overfitting of the model [65].

3.1.1 Implementation details

The model implements and builds upon the PyTorch [66] (version 2.0) and PyTorch Lightning [67] (version 2.0.3) frameworks. Python version 3.11 is used as well as the packages pandas (2.0.3), rdkit (2023.03.2), tensorboard (2.13), cudatoolkit (11.7) and scikit-learn (1.3). PyTorch’s math kernel is used for the calculation of the scaled dot product attention [68]. Functionalities from the PySMILESUtills framework [69] are used to handle tokenisation and dataloading. Token sequences are generated from the predicted probability distributions (called decoding) via beam search [70] with a default beam width of 3.

3.1.2 Tokenisation and vocabulary

The partitioning of SMILES strings into token sequences is done by applying regular expression matching. The following regular expression [38] captures atoms, bonds and special characters such as "(" or "." as one token or subsequence each.

```
"\[[^\]]+\]|Br?|Cl?|N|O|S|P|F|I|b|c|n|o|s|p|\(|\)|\.|=|#|-|\+|\\\|\/|:|~|@|
\?|>|\*|\$|\%[0-9]{2}|[0-9]"
```

Resulting from the pattern matching of a SMILES string is a list of subsequences found in the string that correspond to the patterns defined in the regular expression. The vocabulary lists all subsequences/tokens that are known to the model and assigns each a numerical ID. The list of token literals is then transformed into a list of the corresponding token ids. If the pattern matching has found a subsequence that is not contained in the vocabulary of known tokens and therefore has no ID assigned to it, it is categorised as unknown and assigned the same ID as all other unknown tokens. If the vocabulary does not match the tokens present in the SMILES strings used, this can lead to tokens that occur in the vocabulary not being used during model training and also tokens that are identified by the regular expression in the training data but do not occur in the vocabulary being classified as unknown. To avoid this loss of information a vocabulary generated from the same SMILES data that was used for training is used in this work. It contains 1247 different tokens with "C" (carbon atom) and "c" (aromatic carbon atom) being the most frequent tokens in the dataset.

3.2 Data sources

The data that was used for the forward prediction task, is a subset of the reactions that are contained in the Reaxys database [41]. The reactions were selected considering several aspects. First, only reactions that could be processed and written in SMILES format were considered. Extraction of the SMILES strings was achieved by using Pipeline Pilot [71]. No differentiation between reactants and reagents was attempted due to the facts that no clear distinction between the two is possible and that often important reagents or even reactants are only found in the reaction conditions of the Reaxys database and are not available in a format that could be used for the model training.

All molecules present at the start of a reaction were separated from each other by a "." character and from the product(s) of the reaction by "»". Furthermore, reactions with multiple products were eliminated due to the fact, that the model's objective is to validate the proposed reaction steps in possible synthesis routes, where only reactions with a single product are relevant. This left more than 17.2 million reactions. Reaction data from the USPTO_MIT dataset how it was published and used by Irwin et al. [52] was also used to train models in order to draw comparisons to the current state-of-the-art literature and between different data sources. The Reaxys database contains patent data and with that a presumably large part of the reactions in the USPTO dataset. However, the exact overlap can not easily be determined, for the datasets underwent different processing steps and most likely contain different SMILES representations for the same reactions. Only about 3.5% of the exact SMILES strings from the USPTO data could be

found in the Reaxys data.

All pretraining tasks used chemical structures from the PubChem database [57]. They were taken from Ross et al. [55] in SMILES format. For each of these 111 million molecules the following descriptors were calculated using RDKit:

- Molecular weight (MolWt)
- Wildman-Crippen LogP [72] (MolLogP)
- Number of hydrogen bond donors (NumHDonors)
- Number of hydrogen bond acceptors (NumHAcceptors)
- Fraction of carbon atoms that are sp³ hybridized (FractionCSP3)
- Number of rotatable bonds (NumRotatableBonds)
- Topological polar surface area [73] (TPSA)
- Density of the Morgan fingerprint with radius 2 [74] (FpDensityMorgan2)

This set of descriptors was chosen from the more than 200 descriptors available in rdkit’s modules in an attempt to represent several independent dimensions of chemical space. It has also been used by Fabian et al. [58] in their work on domain-relevant auxiliary tasks for molecular representation learning with language models, where it was chosen as a simple set of commonly used descriptors.

3.3 Data preprocessing

All data in SMILES format from Reaxys and PubChem as well as the calculated molecular descriptors was processed further before being used in the model training and evaluation. The reaction SMILES strings, that were extracted from the Reaxys database were standardised in a first step. In this procedure the protonation state of acids and bases is adjusted to be consistent and lone ions are removed as well as any stereochemical or isotope information. This processing can lead to duplicate reactions occurring in the dataset. For each set of identical SMILES strings, one was kept and the others discarded.

Duplicate reactions were not only found in the processed data from Reaxys but also in the USPTO dataset, that was used in the Chemformer paper. The authors used the USPTO-MIT benchmark set from Jin et al. [37], which includes an atom mapping for the reactions and was filtered for duplicates. However, their processing eliminated the

atom mapping which most probably created the duplicates found in the dataset. Out of the total of 479,035 reactions of which 30 thousand belong to the validation split and 40 thousand to the test split, 5213 occur more than once, 535 reactions can be found in both the training and the validation set and 764 reactions occur both in the training and the test set. This overlap between training and validation or test data is a case of information leakage and causes the accuracy metrics calculated on the test set to be better than can be expected when applying the model to unseen data. Nevertheless, the same training, validation and test split is used in this work, since a primary purpose of the training on USPTO data is the comparison to results published in the literature that were produced on the same test set.

Due to the fact that the computational cost of calculating the attention for a sequence increases quadratically with its length for the vanilla transformer architecture [55], experiments were conducted examining the effect of using a linear complexity attention mechanism [75]. However, the largest part of the token sequences of the reaction data were too short for this measure to achieve a noticeable improvement in computation time.

Instead, the reactions were also filtered regarding the length of the corresponding token sequences. For reasons that are explained in more detail in section 3.4.1, a seemingly small number of longer sequences can increase the computational cost considerably. Therefore, the few very long sequences present in the dataset were eliminated. The maximum sequence length for reactants and product sequences each was set at 256 tokens and 9356 reactions (0.06 %) did not meet this criterion, leaving a total of 15,815,702 reactions.

NextMove's rule based NameRxn software (version 3.7.0) [76] made it possible to categorise a large part of the reaction data into a reaction class hierarchy [77, 78]. An overview over the classification hierarchy can be found in Table 3.2. The classification can have up to three levels, for example the Ugi reactions in the dataset are classified as "2.1.28 Ugi reaction", belonging to the class of Acylations (2) and its subclass of N-acylation to amide (1). It is possible for a reaction to be categorised into two or more classes simultaneously. In the present data all secondary or higher order classes assigned belong to the protection classes.

Close to 9 million reactions were successfully identified. Their distribution over the classes shown in Table 3.2 is given in Figure 3.2. The remaining about seven million reactions, which constitute 45% of the dataset, were labelled as unrecognised.

The category "Resolution" (10) contains a subclass Purification with 117,692 reactions. Upon further inspection, all of these reactions turned out to be of the type $A \rightarrow A$.

Table 3.2: Summary of top-level reaction categories taken from the Reaxys dataset. Reactions with multiple class labels are counted for each of the assigned classes.

Reaction category	Reactions	Percentage	Subclasses
1 - Heteroatom alkylation & arylation	1949871	12.3%	230
2 - Acylation	1614519	10.2%	153
3 - C-C bond forming	1052243	6.7%	352
4 - Aromatic heterocycle formation	391677	2.5%	279
5 - Deprotection	144072	0.9%	29
6 - Protection	1225895	7.8%	91
7 - Reduction	513695	3.2%	57
8 - Oxidation	319313	2.0%	80
9 - Functional group interconversion	949869	6.0%	450
10 - Functional group addition	301466	1.9%	59
11 - Resolution	444325	2.8%	16
12 - Miscellaneous	3	0.0%	2
Total	8748347	55.3%	1798

For the largest part of the reactions classified as Purification this could be identified because the SMILES strings of reactants and products were identical. However, a few cases remained where respectively two slightly different SMILES representations were given for the same planarchiral aromatic molecule. These were inspected and confirmed visually, an example can be seen in the appendix (Figure A.1). Another subclass belonging to the Resolution category is Separation with 256,804 reactions, which all follow the pattern $A + B + C + \dots \longrightarrow A$. These classes of reactions holds no information value for the forward prediction model to learn and can be dropped from the dataset for future work, the presence of these classes in the dataset was only discovered late in the process of this work and could therefore not be considered for the experiments discussed here.

The pretraining data from PubChem was read in SMILES format from Ross et al. [55] using RDKit. Molecules that could not be parsed by RDKit were dropped as well as molecules whose sequence length exceeded 256 tokens. Scikit-learn’s [79] PowerTransformer was applied to the eight molecular descriptors of each molecule (see section 3.2) using Yeo-Johnson’s power transformation to approximate a standard Gaussian distribution [80].

3.4 Training and validation

Training, validation and test splits were randomly assigned for the Reaxys reaction data and the PubChem molecule data. For experiments using USPTO data, the predefined

Figure 3.2: Distribution of the top-level reaction classes in the Reaxys reaction dataset. Reactions with multiple class labels are counted for each of the assigned classes.

split was kept. 90% of the Reaxys reaction data was assigned to the training set and 5% each to the validation and test sets. From the training set, 5 subsets of the following sizes were sampled: 409,035, 1 million, 2 million, 5 million and 10 million reactions. The number of 409,035 reactions matches the size of the USPTO training set. For the pretraining molecule data the training/validation/test split was set at 98%/1%/1%.

The weights of the networks are randomly initialised according to the method by Glorot and Bengio [81] with a uniform distribution. The Adam optimiser was used with the parameters $\beta_1 = 0.9$ and $\beta_2 = 0.999$ for pretraining and finetuning.

All experiments were performed on one GPU at a time. Two different GPU models were used, the NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 and the NVIDIA RTX A6000.

3.4.1 Batching

During training and validation the data was batched with regard to sequence length in order to reduce computational inefficiencies. This is called adaptive bucketing [82] and was able to cut the required training time in half. If a batch contains sequences of different lengths, the shorter sequences are padded with additional <PAD> tokens to the length of the longest sequence. The processing of these irrelevant tokens is a waste of computation and can be reduced, when the sequences are grouped into so-called buckets of similar length. All sequences for a batch are drawn from the same bucket

and are therefore similar in length, so the number of padding tokens is kept low. The data is sorted into 12 buckets, each covering the same width of sequence lengths and the batch size was set to 5000 tokens. For testing or inference a fixed batch-size of 64 sequences was employed.

3.4.2 Pretraining

Four models were pretrained on different combinations of tasks. One was trained on only the masking task, one on masking with simultaneous prediction of the Wildman-Crippen LogP, and two on masking with the simultaneous prediction of all eight molecular descriptors mentioned in section 3.2. For one of the latter two models the representation of the <BOS> token was used to represent the sequence and for the other mean pooling was applied (see section 3.1). The probability for a token to be masked was set to 0.1.

The learning rate for pretraining is scheduled according to the original Transformer schedule with 8000 linear warm-up steps [11, 52]. All models were pretrained for eight million optimiser steps with checkpoints being saved regularly during the training process.

3.4.3 Finetuning

For finetuning, a model with its pretrained parameters is loaded from a checkpoint and a new training process with the new data and task is started. The forward prediction models were trained on reaction datasets of different sizes (409k, 1m, 2m, 5m, 10m, 15m reactions) and origins (Reaxys or USPTO). The learning rate is determined by a cyclic schedule. Using gradient accumulation [83], four backward passes for four batches are performed before updating the parameters. In some cases the models were trained for up to four million optimiser steps. To determine when to stop training a termination criterion was introduced to serve as a guiding principle. It will be presented in the following section.

3.4.4 Evaluation

During validation several metrics are calculated in order to observe the training progress. For one, the validation data is passed through the transformer to calculate its mean value of the loss function without updating the model. This is done every 6.25 thousand training steps. Additionally, three predictions of possible reactions products are

sampled autoregressively for each validation reaction and compared to the target product. Whether the target was found in the n predictions, that were assigned the highest likelihoods by the model, is expressed by the top- n accuracy. To compare the molecules, they are all given in or converted to RDKit’s canonicalised form, so that a comparison of the SMILES strings is sufficient to find identical molecules. In the rare case that two target molecules are given in the USPTO set, a prediction is also considered correct, if the two targets are predicted separately with different assigned likelihoods. Beyond the top-1, top-2 and top-3 accuracies, the accuracy per token is calculated as well as the average number of unique predictions per reaction and the fraction of generated SMILES strings, which are invalid and do not correspond to a chemical structure as determined by RDKit. All of these metrics are computed in every eighth validation epoch at every 50 thousandth training step. The autoregressive sampling of molecules is computationally expensive and scales linearly with the number of molecules that are sampled, which is why only three predictions are generated to keep the time required for training in a reasonable range.

Due to the limitations imposed by computational resource availability, an efficient strategy had to be found to determine when to stop a training run. A simple approach that originated from an empirical analysis of the first training runs proved useful, where the relative change in the top-3 accuracy was monitored. The training was terminated, when the relative change fell below 0.25% for two consecutive validation epochs.

4 Results

4.1 Baseline experiments

In a first experiment, a forward prediction model was trained on the USPTO-MIT benchmark dataset in order to validate the implementation used in this work. First according to the method employed by Irwin et al. [52] and then in the manner described in section 3. The reproduction of Irwin et al. [52]’s results yielded a model, that achieved a 91.2% top-1 accuracy which is on par with the reported accuracy of 91.1% for the randomly initialised model. The model that was trained according to the methods described earlier reached a top-1 accuracy of 87.2%. The difference between these two can be explained with the fact that SMILES augmentation was used by Irwin et al. [52] but not in this work. SMILES augmentation was shown to have a positive effect for training on the USPTO dataset [45]. Tetko et al. [45] claim that multiple representations of the same reaction in the training data eliminate the effect of memorisation and increase generalisation performance.

To check for signs of overfitting to the training data, the calculated loss for each training batch and every validation epoch was recorded. Figure 4.1 shows strong fluctuation in the training loss in contrast to the much smoother curve of the validation loss. This is caused by the different averaging strategies that are used. The training loss is only averaged per batch, while the validation loss is averaged over the whole epoch. The fact that the validation loss passes through a local minimum and begins to increase after a certain point, while the training loss decreases further is often a sign of overfitting and needs to be examined. In this case, this behaviour is not a problem, since the prediction accuracy of product molecules in the validation set, which is the metric of primary interest, keeps improving even when the validation loss begins to increase. The seeming discrepancy between these two metrics is a result of the definition of the cross-entropy loss function. The loss only reaches zero if the predicted probability distribution assigns a probability of 1 to the correct token and 0 to all other vocabulary tokens. For the accuracy however, the only relevant factor is whether the correct token gets assigned the highest probability. So the effect seen in Figure 4.1 is produced, when the model gets more tokens right but is becoming more uncertain in its probability distributions.

Figure 4.1: Development of training and validation loss and validation molecular accuracy over the course of the model training on USPTO data according to Irwin et al. [52]’s methods.

4.1.1 Model variance

When comparing the performance of any models, it is important to keep in mind, that the training of a neural network entails numerous sources of randomness, like the weight initialisation, batch sampling or dropout regularisation. Therefore, different models can differ noticeably from one another in their predictions and therefore performance, even if they were trained following the same methods. Many of these stochastic influences can be controlled by the setting of identical random seeds, but complete reproducibility cannot be guaranteed in PyTorch [84] and hardware plays a role in it as well. Nondeterministic algorithms can be avoided for some operations, however this leads to an increase in runtime and is not feasible for the present use-case. To be able to assess the resulting variance in the trained models, the following trainings of randomly initialised forward reaction prediction models on the Reaxys datasets of different sizes was repeated three times each with a different seed state. The results were aggregated to a mean, minimum and maximum value for these experiments.

4.2 Influence of training set size

The observation that often more training data leads to better performing models raises the question whether a threshold can be reached where enough data is available in a sense that the model reaches its limitations. Reaxys’s large reaction corpus and the

more than 15 million reactions extracted from it make it possible to investigate this issue. Models were randomly initialised and trained on 6 different datasets which are all subsets of the full training set. The smallest sample of the training set contains 409,035 reactions, the same size of the USPTO-MIT training set. The largest set is the full set of 14,241,555 reactions. Moreover, sets with 1 million, 2 million, 5 million and 10 million reactions were examined. Figure 4.2 shows the achieved mean prediction accuracy over the size of the training set.

Figure 4.2: Top-1 accuracy of a randomly initialised model over the size of the dataset it was trained on. Blue markers denote models trained on Reaxys data, orange signifies the same training process but on the USPTO-MIT training set. The errorbars on the Reaxys datapoints show the minimum and maximum values over multiple training runs with different random seeds.

It is clear to see, that more training data increases the prediction accuracy as expected. While the models trained on the smallest dataset predict on average 39.4% of reaction products correctly with their top prediction, the accuracy reaches 56.5% for the models trained on the largest amount of data. The relationship is not linear, however. The gain in accuracy decreases steadily the more data is available for training. At the training set size of around five million reactions a plateau has been reached considering the variance due to the stochasticity in the training. This suggests the existence of a bottleneck concerning the model's complexity or the quality of the data or both. To examine these possibilities further, experiments on models with more trainable parameters or other architectures and experiments using other reaction data would be of interest for future research.

The observation made above permits the conclusion, that five million datapoints are sufficient to train a transformer of the size here chosen in the context of this work on data with the given structure and quality. When remembering that the relatively small

number of 409035 reactions in the USPTO-MIT dataset produced a model that was able to predict more than 90% of reaction outcomes from the corresponding test set correctly, it is evident that the origin of the datasets has a substantial impact on their use in model training.

4.3 Differences between Data Sources

The fact that models trained on USPTO data perform significantly better on unseen USPTO data than models trained on data from the Reaxys corpus perform on unseen Reaxys data could suggest, that the reaction SMILES extracted from the database of the United States Patent and Trademark Office provide more of the information that a model needs to be able to generalise onto unseen data of the same type. On the one hand, this can be explained by a higher quality and uniformity of the USPTO data. Patents undergo thorough examination and any reactions given in a patent are more likely to follow a consistent representation scheme than the reaction data which is collected by Reaxys from various publications. On the other hand, Reaxys's database contains more unique, complex and diverse reactions making it difficult for a model to learn relevant structures and patterns from the data, especially when the training set contains only a small number of examples to learn from. This is clearly the case for the approximately half a million samples in the USPTO sized set, shown in Figure 4.2. It is also more difficult to predict these kinds of unique and complex predictions, because they are not well-represented in the training data. Patent data is not an accurate representation of the average chemical reaction used for real-world purposes. Not all kinds of reactions can be patented or are profitable enough to be patented, the reactions in question are biased toward positive, high-yield reactions [34]. Often when a reaction is patented, a number of very similar variations of the reaction are included in the patent to cover as much ground as possible.

To illustrate this point, a model trained on USPTO data was tested on the Reaxys test set. The Reaxys database collects data from patents as well, therefore it is possible for a reaction that the model has seen during training to be included in the Reaxys test set. This information leakage is very difficult to avoid, because the SMILES strings derived from the same patented reaction can be different for the USPTO and Reaxys datasets. Even though this could distort the predictions, making the model performance seem better than it actually is, the results of this experiment are clear. With a prediction accuracy at around 30%, the model is not able to generalise its learnings, which were sufficient for a 90% accuracy on the USPTO test set, to the much more diverse and complex Reaxys data. Figure 4.3 shows the mean prediction accuracies for the top-1,

Figure 4.3: Mean prediction accuracy of the best pretrained (MLM and SMILES augmentation) Chemformer model published by Irwin et al. [52] on the test set of the Reaxys reaction data. For the individual accuracy the x th most likely prediction alone was evaluated and for the cumulative accuracy the prediction was deemed correct if one of the top- x most likely predictions matched the target.

top-2, top-3, top-5 and top-10 prediction according to the assigned log-likelihood.

In the comparison between the cumulated and individual accuracies the effect of SMILES augmentation during training lowering the number of unique sampled molecules (see section 3.1) can be seen. While the top-1 accuracy is at 30.7%, the top-10 accuracy amounts to 36.9%, meaning that 9 additional predictions per reaction only provided a new correct prediction in 6.2% of cases. Such low prediction accuracies lead to the conclusion, that the USPTO-MIT benchmark set is insufficient for most use cases, because methods developed on it are not transferable to larger, more diverse datasets. A similar observation was made by Torren-Peraire et al. [85] when they evaluated retrosynthesis models on the USPTO-50K benchmark set.

Corroborating evidence for the findings presented here can be found in a work by West-erlund et al. [60], where they trained a Chemformer [52] model for forward prediction on a proprietary dataset of 18 million reactions from AstraZeneca. Most likely this proprietary dataset is much more similar to the Reaxys dataset used here than to the USPTO datasets. The top-1 accuracy they report lies at around 64%, which is comparable to the 56.5% achieved with approximately 15 million reactions in this work.

This highlights a problem in the field, which is the restricted access to reaction data. For academic purposes the USPTO dataset is often the only option, because proprietary

datasets from Reaxys[41] or CAS [42] are increasingly prohibitively expensive. And even these large collections of data are not without their flaws. They each are not able to cover all of the literature and therefore contain systematic gaps where they do not have access to the journals of a specific field of chemistry. Furthermore, the data quality is a limiting factor. The Open Reaction Database [43] is one initiative to encourage sharing of chemical reaction data in a structured format to make it freely and publicly available. The adoption of such a framework by a wide audience would be immensely valuable for reaction prediction modelling and could catalyse progress in the field.

Special attention should also be paid to negative reaction data. Low output experiments are often not reported, even though they could help reduce data bias [48]. The inclusion of such data in the model training, for example labelled with a special token, could prove beneficial for a model’s generalisability and robustness.

4.4 Effects of Pretraining

Pretrained transformers are making impressive progress possible in a number of different research fields [86], and while Irwin et al. [52] were able to produce state of the art results, albeit on the USPTO-MIT dataset, with the Chemformer model that was pretrained on masked and augmented molecule SMILES, the improvement is small. For the forward prediction the difference in accuracy between random initialisation (91.1%) and pretraining (91.8%) was 0.7% [52]. Nevertheless, Ross et al. [55] report that pretraining on a large corpus of chemical SMILES allows a model to learn fundamental properties of chemicals, which could be helpful for the prediction of reactivity.

In the following, five models are compared to one another. One is randomly initialised, four are pretrained on different tasks and all of them are then finetuned on the dataset with five million reactions. The baseline model, which was not pretrained, is the same that was already shown in section 4.2. The dataset with five million reactions was chosen for finetuning, because the analysis of the effect of additional training data in section 4.2 showed that there is only a small benefit in using more data than five million reactions. In order to save computational resources, this compromise was made.

To assess the effects of the pretraining on the training procedure, the development of the prediction accuracy on the validation set during the course of the training process is examined.

4.4.1 Baseline: no pretraining

For the randomly initialised model there is a steep incline of the validation accuracy at the beginning of the training which levels off continuously during the training process, seen in Figure 4.4. Fifty thousand training steps are already enough to reach a top-1 accuracy of about 40%, but 500 thousand further steps are necessary to hit the 50% mark. At 1.6 million steps the termination criterion of a relative change below 0.25% for two consecutive validation epochs has been met for all experiment runs. The trainings are stopped with the highest top-1 validation accuracy at 55.3%. The top-2 and top-3 accuracies reach 65.3 and 69.0% respectively. Also noteworthy is the accuracy per generated token. It follows a similar development like the molecular accuracy but starts at 95.7% and climbs up to 97.6%. Considering that the average target SMILES consists of 45 tokens and all of them have to be generated correctly for the prediction to be counted toward the molecular accuracy, the molecular accuracy is better than the worst case of $0.976^{45} = 0.32$ that could be expected if the incorrect tokens were evenly distributed among the predictions.

Figure 4.4: Molecular and token accuracies on the validation set over the number of training steps for a randomly initialised model trained on five million reactions from Reaxys. This experiment was repeated three times and the errorbars on the curves indicate the minimum and maximum values of the validation metrics for the different models at the same training step.

Looking at the standard deviation between the multiple runs of the training with different random states, the variance and influence of stochasticity is largest at the beginning of the training. This can be explained by the random initialisation, which naturally has the greatest effect in the beginning, and the random batching of training sequences.

The first batches that the models are given, are different for each model but latest with the passing of one training epoch, all models have seen the same data, weakening this stochastic influence.

Based on the percentage of generated sequences that are not valid SMILES strings, we can assess the models ability to operate within the grammatical rules of the SMILES notation. It improves steadily throughout the training process from 2.5% to 0.7%. It is also connected to the number of unique molecules that are predicted per reaction, which also improves during training but not much. With on average 2.9 predictions out of three that are valid SMILES and distinct from one another, the model fares much better in this regard than models from the literature that were trained using SMILES augmentation (see sections 3.1 and 4.1) [52]. A model trained on augmented SMILES has not necessarily learned that multiple SMILES representations exist for a molecule and could therefore suggest different SMILES for the same molecule. An equal treatment of different SMILES strings describing the same molecule influences the predicted token probability distributions in a way that equivalent SMILES strings are more readily sampled by the beam search algorithm than SMILES representing alternative products.

With this knowledge about the capabilities of the baseline model, the next step is to examine the influence of pretraining with the simplest pretraining task.

4.4.2 Masked Language Modelling

Two model checkpoints from the masked language modelling (MLM) pretraining on the PubChem molecules were finetuned, the last checkpoint that was pretrained for 8 million steps and the first checkpoint, which was saved after 50 thousand pretraining steps. The training curves for both are plotted in Figure 4.5 together with that for the baseline model.

While the model pretrained for eight million steps performs better during validation up to the point of about one million steps, they then fall behind, because the baseline model shows a consistently higher slope. The pretraining seems to have imparted some information about structures and patterns in chemical data of the SMILES format to the model, that is able to give the model a headstart in the training of forward reaction prediction. However, this prior knowledge prevents the model from finding a set of weights that performs on the same level as the weights that were randomly initialised. Thinking about the optimisation process behind the model training, this means, that the pretraining leads the model into a minimum of its loss function, that corresponds to a better performing forward prediction model than a randomly initialised model that

Figure 4.5: Molecular accuracy on the validation set over the course of the finetuning process after 50 thousand and eight million steps MLM pretraining.

has not been trained. However, this different starting point causes the pretrained model to approach a different local minimum of the forward prediction’s loss function than the randomly initialised model approaches. Whether the absolute minimum is found at any point can not be known, but since the randomly initialised model performs better, its weights belong to a point in the optimisation hyperplane that is better suited to the intended application.

The model that was finetuned after only 50 thousand pretraining steps, does not show the improved performance at the start of the finetuning process compared to the baseline model. However, it does exhibit the decreased slope of the model pretrained for eight million steps, therefore remaining behind the baseline model at all times. This amount of pretraining was not able to impart useful patterns of chemical data, but still brought about a less favourable training development. Consequently, the number of pretraining steps has a considerable influence. Eight million steps were chosen as the default pretraining duration after a comparison of the finetuning behaviour after one million, two million, four million, six million and eight million pretraining steps showed no more significant change between six and eight million steps (see Figure A.2 in the appendix).

MLM on SMILES for individual molecules can be seen critically, because context within a sequence, which plays an important part in MLM for NLP, is not given in the same way for a chemical structure in the SMILES notation. Furthermore, molecules separate from their text representation do not have a context either, which sets SMILES even further apart from natural language. From the MLM self-supervised task the model can learn

the grammar of SMILES, but arguably not much about the molecules it sees.

4.4.3 Prediction of Molecular Descriptors

As has already been mentioned in section 2.4, the prediction of molecular descriptors in combination with MLM aims to provide an approximation of context of the form in which it occurs in natural languages.

4.4.3.1 Number of Predicted Descriptors

At first, only the prediction of the Wildmann-Crippen LogP was combined with MLM for pretraining, but this proved to be detrimental to the model performance during finetuning for forward prediction. The Wildman-Crippen LogP was chosen because it is a well-known and widely used model for atom-based calculation of the logarithmic partition coefficient of water and octanol [87], a physical property that is used to characterise molecules regarding for example pharmacokinetics or environmental risk. For comparison, a model was pretrained on predicting all eight molecular descriptors, that were introduced in section 3.2, simultaneously with MLM. This model fared much better. Both models used the representation of the begin-of-sequence token to represent the whole sequence during pretraining (see section 3.1). The training curves for both models are compared to each other and to the randomly initialised model in Figure 4.6.

While the prediction of only the Wildman-Crippen LogP during pretraining influences the model negatively during finetuning, the combination of the eight different descriptors is beneficial in the early training stage, but loses most of its effect after a while of finetuning. The information imparted during pretraining on only the cLogP seems not to be representative of the information that is needed for reaction prediction and poses a hindrance to the model. However, the interaction between the different descriptors during pretraining apparently strikes a balance between different aspects and dimensions that are relevant for reactivity and is able to provide the model with learned patterns it can use during finetuning. It should be mentioned that the physical validity of the calculated descriptors is limited, since they are computational approximations of quantities that are much more difficult to determine. However, this should not be a hindrance for their use to provide context to the chemical structures during pretraining.

With the cLogP, number of hydrogen bond acceptors and donors and the topological polar surface area the polarity of a molecule is represented, while molecular weight, number of rotatable bonds, topological polar surface area and the fraction of sp³ hy-

Figure 4.6: Molecular accuracy on the validation set over the course of the finetuning process after 8 million steps each of MLM pretraining combined with the prediction of only the cLogP and the prediction of molecular weight, cLogP, number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors, number of rotatable bonds, fraction of sp³ hybridised carbon, topological polar surface area and density of the Morgan fingerprint. All properties are encoded on the BOS-token and five million reactions are used for finetuning.

bridized carbons hold information about the size and shape of the molecule. Since the Morgan fingerprint is used for example to predict biological activity, its density together with the number of sites for possible hydrogen bonds, fraction of sp³ hybridized carbon atoms and the SMILES representation could potentially provide insights into a molecule’s (biological) reactivity.

The observation that the context provided by the clogP value can harm the finetuning performance so clearly is unexpected, since providing any additional information should help the model interpret and align the molecular structures it is fed. As the begin-of-sequence token, which carries the representation used for the descriptor prediction during pretraining, does not serve an explicit function in the finetuning task, the major influence should stem from the MLM task, which is in turn influenced by the context of the molecular descriptors during pretraining. Further research is needed in this area to understand these relationships.

4.4.3.2 Sequence Representation

In addition to the models described in the previous section, which use the BOS token for sequence representation, a model using mean pooling was pretrained on MLM and

prediction of the eight descriptors. The mean pooled model performed slightly worse during finetuning, but the absolute difference in molecular accuracy amounted only to 0.16% and is not conclusive (visualisation in Figure A.3). A difference between the two pooling strategies could stem from a more evenly distributed involvement of weights when averaging the representations over a sequence. In the following only the pooling method using the BOS token will be considered further.

Overall, the pretraining on this simple set of descriptors has a small positive effect on the training of reaction prediction, but since it requires a lot of data and computational resources, it is not an effective strategy to improve forward prediction modelling. When looking back at Figure 4.2, where we can see that using more than five million reactions for training does not significantly improve the achieved average prediction accuracy any further, these results regarding the effectiveness of pretraining fit in. In the case that additional data for the target task is not able to improve model performance, it is unlikely for additional data for a different task to be able to do just that.

4.4.4 Influence of Finetuning Dataset Size

Even though the pretraining methods examined here have proven to be inefficient when finetuning on five million reactions, they can still be useful, if not much finetuning data is available like in the case of the USPTO dataset. To explore this so called low-data regime, two pretrained models were finetuned on datasets smaller than the five million reactions used previously, the model pretrained on MLM alone and the model trained on MLM in combination with the prediction of all eight descriptors.

The positive effect of pretraining using only masked language modelling that was observed in the literature on the USPTO data [52] also occurs for the Reaxys training data when using the smallest, USPTO sized dataset of 409 thousand reactions for finetuning. Unlike for the larger dataset, the MLM pretrained model does not fall behind the not-pretrained model after a certain amount of training steps, but the pretrained model shows an accuracy only 2.4% (absolute) better than the randomly initialised model trained on the small dataset. The MLM pretraining loses its effect, when finetuning on the Reaxys training set with two million reactions, where the randomly initialised model outperforms the pretrained model after a while. Therefore, the range in which MLM pretraining alone positively influences the finetuning process is limited to small finetuning datasets. Table 4.1 contrasts the results of the pretrained models with the randomly initialised models for the different datasets.

When finetuning the model pretrained on MLM and descriptor prediction, the model

Table 4.1: Top-1 molecular accuracy for the pretrained models finetuned on datasets of different sizes and the random initialised models for comparison.

Reactions in finetuning set	random	MLM	MLM + descriptor prediction
409,035	40.4%	42.8%	43.1%
1 mio	46.4%	47.9%	48.9%
2 mio	51.6%	51.6%	52.2%
5 mio	55.1%	54.8%	55.6%
14.24 mio	56.9%	55.4%	56.5%

Figure 4.7: Difference in top-1 accuracy between pretrained and randomly initialised models for training/finetuning on datasets of different sizes. Pretrained models in question are the model pretrained on only MLM and the model pretrained on MLM in combination with the prediction of all eight calculated descriptors using the representation of the BOS token.

finetuned with the smallest Reaxys dataset fared 2.7% better in absolute percentage points than its not pretrained counterpart. For finetuning on larger datasets it performs consistently better than the randomly initialised model but the absolute difference between the models' performance decreases. Figure 4.7 shows the difference in top-1 accuracy between the pretrained and randomly initialised models over the number of reactions in the training set.

In conclusion, the combination of MLM with descriptor prediction performs better than MLM on its own also for finetuning on smaller datasets than five million reactions. It is furthermore able to improve model performance for finetuning on two million reactions or more, where the pretraining with only MLM is not. For downstream tasks with small amounts of available data its use could be helpful even though the improvement

compared to random initialisation is not especially prominent in the case of forward reaction prediction as the downstream task.

4.5 Evaluation of model performance

Up until now the determining metric for performance was the mean accuracy of the predicted molecules. This is also predominant in the relevant literature, because it is the simplest and most intuitive way of aggregating over all predictions. Since the reaction data is so vast and diverse, it is not possible to draw conclusions from single prediction instances. Nevertheless, it can be insightful to inspect exemplary reactions in order to get an overview of challenges and intricacies that a model faces. In the following, predictions are analysed using metrics beyond the mean accuracy and some examples are shown and discussed.

In section 3.3 the class hierarchy of NextMove’s NameRxn software was already introduced. Based on this scheme, the reaction predictions can be evaluated reaction class wise. The randomly initialised model trained on the complete training data was used to generate predictions based on the reactant SMILES in the test set which are categorised in Figure 4.8. The mean top-1, top-2 and top-3 accuracies amount to 60.4%, 70.9% and 74.8% respectively. But a look at the averages per reaction class shows substantial dif-

Figure 4.8: Mean top-1, top-2 and top-3 molecular prediction accuracies per reaction class on the test dataset.

ferences between different classes. While acylation reactions are predicted correctly with the top-1 molecule in 91.2% of the cases, functional group additions reach only

19.9%. Functional group interconversions rank low as well with a 44.5% top-1 accuracy, followed by the reactions which could not be recognised with 45.4%.

A look at the finer granulated reaction classes and their respective accuracies reveals even greater disparities between the classes. Figure 4.9a shows the top-1 accuracies of the lowest level reaction classes (e.g. 2.1.28 Ugi) on the test set and Figure 4.9b the accuracies of the middle level of classes (e.g. 2.1 N-Acylation to amide) over the frequency with which they occur in the whole dataset. To be included, a class needs to be represented in the test set with at least 1 reaction. 1585 lowest-level classes from the total of 1799 and all of the 71 mid-level classes are present in the test set. A relationship between

Figure 4.9: Top-1 accuracies of the finer granulated reaction classes plotted over their frequency in the dataset. Marker colours in (a) represent the density of points at the position of the marker. The unrecognized reactions are represented by the x-marker.

predictive accuracy and frequency in the training data for a specific reaction class is not observed. The Pearson correlation coefficient measuring linear correlation between the two variables is small with a value of 0.11 for the low-level classes or 0.23 for the mid-level classes (unrecognised reactions were excluded). Behind the unrecognised reactions, the class carboxylic acid + amine condensation is the most frequent with 363,447 instances and a top-1 accuracy of 95.5%. For example the very small class of fluoro to thiocyanato functional group interconversions only occurred in the test set with both its two instances. The model still predicted one of the two correctly. This can be interpreted as a sign of the model's generalisation capabilities.

It is to be expected that reactions that could not be recognised by the NameRxn software show a lower than average prediction accuracy, since they have already proven to be too complex or too divergent for an expert system to identify. This could be due to inadequate notation of the reactions or reactions being too new or niche to have been considered in the development of the rule system behind NameRxn. These reactions

therefore include transformations and patterns that are more likely to be too noisy or not well-represented in the training data and difficult for the forward prediction model to infer from the data.

For the prediction of reactions where a functional group is added to the molecule, several aspects can be responsible for the poor performance of the predictions. Even though functional group addition is the second smallest highest level class in the dataset, it is unlikely that the model suffers from a lack of data to learn from. Figure 4.9 already shows that there is no correlation between model performance and frequency in the dataset for a reaction class. Therefore, imbalance in the data is unlikely to be the sole cause for the model's difficulties with additions of functional groups. A different explanation could be that the addition of a functional group can often occur at multiple sites within a molecule and is more dependent on specific reaction conditions than other reaction types. Since the reaction conditions are not known to the model, this is a problem it cannot be expected to overcome. It is especially prominent in the predictions of nitration reactions, one of the biggest subclasses of the functional group addition class. For nitration reactions the average top-1 accuracy is only 12.8% and the following example in Figure 4.10 illustrates the difficulties with this reaction class.

Figure 4.10: A nitration reaction from the Reaxys database and the top 3 predictions of the product.

In the reaction SMILES string only one reactant is given, which contains multiple functional groups able to undergo different reactions. Without the reaction conditions, which are given in the source as "with tert.-butylnitrite in acetonitrile at 20 °C" [88] it is impossible to confidently determine the reaction outcome. The model has to rely on the statistics it has learnt during training, which transformations are most common for single reactants featuring the given set of functional groups. In this case it guesses right and predicts the given target with the prediction it assigned the third highest likelihood to. The other two predictions are, however, chemically valid and equally plausible given the information that the model had available.

On average the nitration reactions in the dataset have 1.19 reactants, indicating that the

Figure 4.11: Top-1 accuracy over the average number of given reactants aggregated over the different individual reaction classes. The marker colour indicates the density of markers in that position and the area of the markers indicates the number of reactions in the respective class.

situation described above applies to a larger part of the reaction class. Not only the nitration reactions are affected by this, other classes such as the Prilezhaev epoxidation, where a peroxycarboxylic acid reacts with an alkene group, also show a low prediction accuracy (20.8%) and an average number of reactants close to one (1.04). In Figure 4.11 the top-1 molecular accuracy of all different reaction classes on the test set is plotted over their average number of reactants that are given in the data.

The classes cluster around the average reactant numbers of one, two and three, although the number of reaction classes with on average close to three reactants is by far the smallest. While accuracies range between zero and one and concentrate toward the bottom of the scale for reactions with approximately one reactant, reactions with more reactants tend to perform better with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.45 between the two variables. One reason for this is that the problem of missing reactants described above is less common, when more reactants are given and another reason could be that with more reactants, the model has fewer possibilities to combine all given reactants into a sensible reaction. That all molecules given in the reaction SMILES participate in the ground truth reactions is a bias of the model and should be kept in mind.

This shows that the inclusion of reaction conditions in the modelling process is crucial for these types of reactions. It also highlights the fact that the model has no notion of conservation of mass. This is to be expected because the majority of recorded reactions in the data are not given in a balanced form. On the one hand, this lets the model deal

with missing reactants and reagents as seen with the nitration reaction above. On the other hand, this leads to irrelevant predictions in the case that all reactants and reagents are listed (For an example see Figure 4.17).

The reactions belonging to the resolution class are problematic as well since they are not all reactions in the usual sense of the word. Besides the purification and separation reactions that were already discussed in section 3.3 and found to be exclusively of the types $A \longrightarrow A$ and $A + B + C + \dots \longrightarrow A$, other subclasses such as hydration, dehydration or ammonium cleavage reactions are part of the resolution type. However, purification and separation reactions dominate the resolution class and are questionable for the use in a reaction prediction model.

This concludes an overview over the models' general capabilities. Further areas of interest concern the intended use cases for the models and are discussed in the following

4.5.1 Example reactions relevant to retrosynthesis

It should be kept in mind for the model evaluation, that one of the main purposes of the forward prediction model is to validate proposed reaction steps in retrosynthesis. Retrosynthesis tools have known weaknesses which include ring-forming reactions, rearrangements, Ugi reactions and disconnections where competing functional groups are formed in the reactants [60]. It is prudent to specifically examine the forward prediction performance on these types of reactions, in order to assess whether the forward prediction model is suited to the task.

In Figure 4.8 it can be seen, that the average prediction accuracies for C-C bond forming and aromatic heterocycle formation are quite high, indicating a sufficient capability for validating proposed ring-forming reaction steps. For rearrangements the results are mixed. Some types of rearrangements work well for the model such as the Wolff rearrangement (72%), while others perform below average, for example the Meinwald rearrangement (27%).

Ugi reactions are predicted exceptionally well with all 27 of the Ugi reactions in the test set being predicted correctly on the first try. With four participating functional groups, they present a characteristic pattern that the model was able to pick up on. Westerlund et al. [60] make a similar observation and give the limited reaction space of Ugi reactions as an explanation. The reaction shown in Figure 4.12 is an Ugi reaction used for ring-forming and could be correctly predicted with the model's first guess. Also of interest is the model's top-2 prediction, which gets assigned a significantly lower likelihood of 0.00019 than the likelihood of 0.90 of the primary product, but is a possible

side product of the Passerini reaction. The Passerini reaction competes with the Ugi reaction as it involves a carboxylic acid, ketone and isocyanide which are all prerequisites for the Ugi reaction as well [89].

Figure 4.12: A correctly predicted Ugi reaction with the second most likely prediction being a possible side product of the Passerini reaction.

Finally, Figure 4.13 shows a reaction, that was proposed by a retrosynthesis tool as part of a synthesis tree, but is not successful in practice because of competing functional groups. The tool has proposed connecting the two reactants by a transesterification reaction. Seen individually, this is a feasible transformation, however the reactant bearing the ether group also contains a primary amine, which is a much stronger nucleophile than the oxygen in the ether group and prevents the reaction from taking place at the ether group. While the retrosynthesis prediction struggles with this situation and a binary feasibility classifier trained on positive and negative reaction data was not able to identify the reaction as infeasible, the forward reaction prediction recognises the higher reactivity of the amine group and predicts single or even double alkylation of the amine nitrogen (Figure 4.13).

Training data for the feasibility filter relevant to this reaction is likely scarce, because it is apparent to an organic chemist, that this reaction will not work. Therefore, the number of recorded experiments examining the reactivity of such reactants will most probably be very small.

This demonstrates the ability of the forward reaction prediction to act as an additional filter for the computer-aided proposition of synthesis routes, identifying reaction steps that are likely to fail in the laboratory and complementing the capabilities of existing binary classifiers for validation of reaction steps.

Figure 4.13: A reaction proposed during retrosynthesis route search, which is not experimentally feasible and the predictions of the forward reaction model for the given reactants.

4.5.2 Uncertainty estimation for predictions

Uncertainty estimation aims to provide an indication regarding the reliability of a prediction. With the mean prediction accuracy, predictions are counted as either correct or false and there is no differentiation between predictions where all tokens except for one are correct and predictions where all tokens are incorrect, both are simply counted towards the false predictions. The prediction accuracy per token which ranges around 98% suggests that a substantial number of predictions could contain fragments present in the target molecule (see section 4.4.1). To analyse this further with more nuance, a similarity score is calculated for pairs of predictions and target molecules. The widely-used Jaccard-Tanimoto coefficient [90, 91] is well suited to derive similarities from binary molecule fingerprints [92]. It is calculated using the default RDKit fingerprint generator with a fingerprint size of 2048 and a number of two bits per feature. In Figure 4.14 the likelihood of predictions from the test set is plotted over the Tanimoto similarity coefficient of the predicted molecule to the target molecule.

For top-1, top-2 and top-3 predictions, the most common value of the Tanimoto similarity coefficient by far is 1, followed by 0 with considerable fewer occurrences. Between 0 and 1 the similarity coefficient of the top-1 prediction is distributed approximately uniformly, while the second and third most likely predictions are slightly more broadly distributed around the maximum value of 1, which is less frequent for top-2 and top-3 than for top-1.

The top-2 and top-3 predictions are more similar to the target, if the model predicted the

Figure 4.14: Relationship between Likelihood of a sampled prediction and its Tanimoto similarity coefficient to the target product.

correct product with the top-1 prediction and was confident in its prediction (higher likelihood). Correlating the similarity coefficient with the log likelihood produces a Pearson correlation coefficient of $\rho_1 = 0.54$ for the top-1 predictions but only $\rho_2 = 0.03$ and $\rho_3 = -0.001$ for top-2 and top-3. Seemingly the model is able to give a good estimate whether its predictions will be correct with the log likelihood for the top-1 predictions but not for top-2 and top-3.

The correlations are different if all predictions are removed for which higher ranking predictions for the same reaction have already predicted the correct products, yielding $\rho_2 = 0.31$ and $\rho_3 = 0.15$. This could be caused by nonsensical predictions, which are generated if the model is very confident in its top prediction and is not able to produce a meaningful alternative. Consequently, the log likelihood of lower ranking predictions loses validity, if a correct prediction has already been made. This knowledge can be helpful when trying to assess the trustworthiness of a concrete prediction. Further research into the interpretability of the predictions' likelihoods could prove valuable, should it be the case that the likelihoods reflect on the possibility of side reactions.

4.6 Prediction of reaction byproducts and side products

A very valuable predictive capability of generative deep learning models is the anticipation of byproducts and side products that are potentially generated in the course of a reaction. Byproducts are produced as the direct result of the desired reaction and are relatively straightforward to foresee compared to side products, which are the result of side reactions [93]. However, often neither side nor byproducts are included in the recorded reaction data. In the following, it is examined, whether the models trained in this work are already suited to this task. Furthermore, a model trained to predict

reaction products with the additional given information of what type of reaction is expected is explored specifically considering regioselectivity.

4.6.1 Examples from textbooks and the literature

As a starting point, simple reactions that are known to give more than one product were chosen from textbooks [94, 95] and the literature and predictions were generated based on the reactants. The first example in Figure 4.15 is an electrophilic addition of hydrogen chloride to an alkene. These reactions produce a primary product according

Figure 4.15: An electrophilic addition reaction from [94] yielding a recorded major product and a minor product according to Markovnikov's rule.

to Markovnikov's rule, but in this case small quantities of the Anti-Markovnikov product are formed as well. The forward reaction prediction model predicts the major product correctly but the minor product is not found in the top-5 predictions. Instead, the addition of water and a rearrangement of the alkene are proposed, which are theoretically possible but depend on other reaction conditions. For a similar reaction involving an unbranched alkene and hydrogen bromide, that produces two products in equal measure, both were predicted at the two top positions. The reaction scheme can be found in the appendix, Figure A.4.

The following Grignard reaction (Figure 4.16) illustrates the importance of reactant concentrations. In the work where this reaction was published one equivalent of Grignard reagent was added to the dichlorobenzene, giving primarily the mono-alkylated benzene product [96]. Since the model does not have this information, it assigns the highest likelihood to the alkylation of both chlorine groups, followed by the mono-alkylation. The third prediction shows the connection between two benzene rings, a side reaction that can occur if the reaction conditions are not carefully controlled.

Figure 4.16: Grignard reaction for the mono-alkylation of dichlorobenzene.

For the reaction in Figure 4.17 below, where the peroxy acid is able to react with the double bond according to the Prilezhaev reaction or with the ketone via the Baeyer-Villiger oxidation to form a lactone, none of the three recorded products were predicted by the model [96]. Instead, the forward reaction prediction yields multiple variations of the addition of the peroxy acid to the double bond, one of which contains an iodine atom, that does not occur in the reactants. Both Prilezhaev reaction and Baeyer-Villiger

Figure 4.17: Reaction of a cyclical ketone containing an alkene group with a peroxy acid.

oxidation are reaction classes where the prediction accuracies on the test set are below average with a top-1 value of 21.0% for the Prilezhaev reaction and 13.8% for the Baeyer-Villiger oxidation. Considering that the average number of given reactants is close to one for both reaction types (1.04 and 1.09 respectively), it is a reasonable conclusion that the peroxy carboxylic acid is not given in most of the reactions even though there are 28.205 Prilezhaev epoxidations and 4,338 Baeyer-Villiger oxidations in the complete dataset of training, validation and test. Therefore, the model has not learned that a

peroxy carboxylic acid is used to perform these reactions and is not able to make the correct prediction although all necessary molecules are supplied in the SMILES string for the prediction. In effect, this means that these types of reactions can not be predicted, much less their side reactions, because the characteristic patterns are not included in the training data.

From these examples we can see, that the anticipation of side products works well for reaction types that the model predicts with high accuracies. On the other hand, for reactions where the major product can not be predicted correctly or only with the top-2 or lower ranking prediction, the generation of additional predictions holds no insights into potential other products.

4.6.2 Reactions extracted from US patents with given byproducts

The examples given above have been concentrated on the prediction of side products. Nevertheless, byproducts are equally important to be considered in synthesis planning. In the USPTO reaction data, a small part of the reactions of about 1% are given with two products which are byproducts to each other. These were given to the model to predict and the results were analysed. In the data, the products are given in the form of "SMILES1.SMILES2" to denote distinct molecules using the notation that is also used for multiple reactants. However, the model trained on Reaxys data has not seen reactions with multiple products during its training and therefore does not predict byproducts in this form. Instead, the products occur in different sampled molecules if both are predicted. Of the 471 reactions with two target products, 37% are predicted correctly in the sense that both products occur separately in the top 5 predictions. One of the targets is predicted in 67% of cases. Byproduct prediction has already been targeted with separate approaches in the literature, which could be better suited to the task [97].

4.6.3 Reaction class specific predictions

To circumvent the problem that reactions pose, whose major product can not be accurately predicted and to gain more insights into questions of regioselectivity, a specialised model was trained to this effect. For this all reactions SMILES were extended with a special token representing the reaction class as determined by NameRxn at the first position of the sequence. For reactions that could not be recognized by NameRxn the token <0.0> was used. It can be hypothesised that the model can use this additional information to determine the chemoselectivity and intended reaction motive (see section 4.5 and Figure 4.10) and focus on regioselectivity with its predictions. The prediction accuracies

with this model for reactants with the prepended reaction class token are plotted in Figure 4.18.

Figure 4.18: Top-1, top-2 and top-3 mean prediction accuracies on the test set for the prediction with lowest level NameRxn reaction class information as additional input accumulated over the highest level NameRxn classes.

In comparison to the predictions without the additional token (see Figure 4.8), the accuracy improved substantially for all recognised reaction classes. Even the prediction accuracy of reactions that could not be identified by NameRxn rose slightly. The corresponding label <0.0> holds little information for human interpretation, but the information that these reactions do not clearly belong in one of the categories the model knows about seems to be enough to improve its predictions.

In Figure 4.19 it can be seen that the improvement in accuracy affected especially the reaction classes with an average number of reactants close to one. Indicating that the problem of missing reactants/reagents can be alleviated with this model.

In general, with top-1 predictions that high, the room for improvement with top-2 and top-3 predictions is small. Additionally, the average number of unique molecules predicted per reaction decreased from 2.9 to 2.8 out of three compared to the model without specification of the reaction class. It follows that it is much more common than before that the model generates different SMILES representations of the same molecule, because it is heavily influenced by the additional reaction class token and narrows its predictions onto the chemical space that it has seen during training for the specific reaction type. The high accuracies suggest that the prediction of chemoselectivity is more difficult to the model than predicting the regioselectivity.

Figure 4.19: Top-1 accuracy of the model trained with indication of the NameRxn assigned reaction class over the average number of given reactants aggregated over the different individual reaction classes. The marker colour indicates the density of markers in that position and the area of the markers indicates the number of reactions in the respective class.

To confirm the hypothesis that this model focuses on regioselectivity with its predictions by way of example, the nitration reaction which was already discussed in section 4.5 is revisited. The top five predictions for the reaction are shown below in Figure 4.20 and are all products of nitration via electrophilic aromatic substitution reactions. The top prediction matches the target molecule, while the further predictions propose twofold nitration and varying positioning of the nitro groups.

Figure 4.20: Predictions for the nitration reaction shown in Figure 4.10, when the model input is supplemented with the token representing nitration.

For the formerly in all predictions incorrect Prilezhaev and Baeyer-Villiger reaction from section 4.6.1 (shown in Figure 4.17), a partial success is achieved with the incorporation

of the reaction class labels. When the token indicating a Prilezhaev reaction is prepended to the reactants the model predicts the correct transformation of the alkene group (top row in Figure 4.21) and when the token symbolising the Baeyer-Villiger oxidation is used instead, the transformation of the keto group to the lactone is predicted (bottom row in Figure 4.21). Nevertheless, the experimentally recorded major product, where both transformations occur is never predicted. In this case the specification of an expected reaction hampers the prediction of the major product, because only one reaction class token can be given at a time and the model then limits itself in favour of the specified reaction class, disregarding other potentially valid options.

Predictions for Prilezhaev reaction type:

Predictions for Baeyer-Villiger oxidation:

Figure 4.21: Predictions for the combined Prilezhaev and Baeyer-Villiger oxidation reaction from [96] (see Figure 4.17), when specific tokens representing the reaction types (top row: Prilezhaev, bottom row: Baeyer-Villiger) are added to the model input.

It should be noted that the model can lead to incorrect predictions if the reaction class label is not correct. For example for the reaction proposed by a retrosynthesis tool, which was discussed in section 4.5.1 (see Figure 4.13), the incorrect product is compelled in the model by providing the corresponding ether halide coupling token to the model input, shown in Figure 4.22. The influence of the given token is stronger than its learned patterns, which were able to correctly assign the higher reactivity to the primary amine before. Therefore, the predictions of this model should always be considered together with the predictions of a model which does not rely on the specification of a reaction class.

Finally, an alternative approach to get predictions of side and byproducts was investigated by training on reactions with multiple products using two different strategies to combine them with the previously used training set of single product reactions.

Figure 4.22: Predicted reaction products for the two reactants proposed in Figure 4.13 with reaction class specified in model input. Top: Ether halide coupling specified, Bottom: Amide Schotten-Baumann specified

4.6.4 Training on reactions with multiple reported products

The Reaxys database contains a large amount of reactions for which multiple product species are given. About 2.8 million of these could be extracted and were cleaned according to the procedures described in section 3.3. They were removed from the main dataset used and discussed so far, since the purpose of the model is to validate proposed reaction pathways for synthesis coming from a retrosynthesis tool, where only reactions yielding one product are of relevance. Only for the following experiments were they included in model training. It should be mentioned that no information on the ratio between different products is included in the dataset, which could be seen as an oversimplification of the problem.

One approach was to use a model that was trained on the full forward prediction training dataset not containing multi product reactions without pretraining, use its weights as a starting point and then train the model on only the reaction data with multiple products as targets. This can also be seen as a form of finetuning for the specific task of predicting multiple products. In another approach the reaction data with one target per reaction and the data with multiple targets was combined into one dataset on which a randomly initialised model was trained. To counteract the imbalance between the much more frequent 14.2 million reactions with a single product and the underrepresented 2.8 million reactions with multiple products, the reactions with multiple products were oversampled, so that each of those reactions appeared three times in the dataset and they constituted approximately a third of all reactions [98].

Overall, both approaches produced comparable results in the evaluation on a test set of 50% single product and 50% multiple product reactions, but differences between them have to be noted. While the model that was finetuned on the multiple products reactions predicted between two and four products in all cases, even though the number of products in the ground truth ranges between one and six molecules, the model that was trained simultaneously on both types of reactions is better able to predict the number of products that are given in the ground truth.

However, even though the model trained on the combined dataset is able to correctly predict when only one product molecule is expected, the quality of its predictions for the reactions with single products suffers compared to a baseline model only trained on single product reactions. It achieves a top-1 molecular accuracy of 54% compared to the 60% of the baseline model. This is not the case for the model finetuned on the multi product reactions, it performs on par with the baseline model. Yet, since it always predicts multiple products in one SMILES string, the correct product has to be chosen and the rest discarded to match the ground truth of reactions with only a single product. Effectively, this affords the model more opportunities to generate predictions and a higher chance that the correct one will be among them. Because this does not constitute a fair comparison, a different approach to score the predictions could be to count the inclusion of one incorrect molecule as an incorrect prediction, independent of the number of correct molecules in the prediction. Such considerations have to be made taking into account the intended use of a model.

During preprocessing, the data with multiple given products showed significantly different characteristics from the data with singular products. A much higher percentage of almost 76% of reactions was not recognised by NameRxn and of the recognised reactions, a large part belong to the resolution class, which has been established to be of little value for the prediction of reactivity (section 3.3). Apart from the possibility that the NameRxn software could have more difficulties identifying reactions with multiple products, this observation suggests that the quality of this set of reaction data is not as high as for the reactions with only one specified product. This supposition could partly explain the poor prediction performance on the reactions with multiple products. The model that was trained simultaneously on single and multi product reactions was able to predict all given products correctly in 2.2% and at least one in 27.2% of cases. The model that was trained with an additional finetuning step performed better with correct predictions in 3.6% and 31.8% of cases respectively, but these accuracies are far from the results in the range of 50 and 60% that were achieved on the single product reactions. They are also not much higher than the performance of the baseline model, which has not seen any of the reactions leading to multiple products in its training procedure and predicts at least one target correctly in 17.4% of tested reactions.

Considering these results, the two investigated training processes on reaction data with multiple products appear futile, because the resulting model is either able to predict how many products occur but shows a decreased prediction accuracy or it is able to predict more products correctly but not the number of expected products. The number of given products is also heavily dependent on the individual publications from which the reactions were extracted and completeness or consistency can not be expected. Overall, the discussed approaches show no advantage over the sampling of multiple molecules with different likelihoods via beam search.

These experiments conclude the evaluation of the forward prediction models for prediction of side and by products. It is possible to gain indications concerning possible side products and predict byproducts to the major product with the examined models by sampling more than one prediction using the beam search algorithm and consulting the assigned log likelihoods. However, such findings are in no way reliable and vary with the available training data. Nevertheless, such insights can be valuable for the design of a synthesis route and should be examined in the process. For future research endeavors addressing these problems the curation of specialised datasets and the utilisation of other sampling methods could be promising.

5 Conclusion and Outlook

In this thesis, forward reaction prediction using a BART transformer architecture was explored, developing and evaluating models trained on proprietary data from Reaxys, diverging from the USPTO dataset commonly used in the literature. The models exhibited the ability to replicate results from the literature on the USPTO dataset but displayed significant performance discrepancies when applied to proprietary data. This first major finding of this work underscores the inadequacy of relying solely on the USPTO dataset for training models intended for real-world applications in synthesis chemistry, but also the need to find a consistent framework for the reporting of chemical reaction data, so that it can be used effectively for data-driven modelling. The Open Reaction Database [43] is one initiative to encourage sharing of chemical reaction data in a structured format to make it freely and publicly available, which could have a great impact.

With access to over 14 million reactions for training, it was observed that increased data availability correlated positively with prediction performance. However, beyond a certain threshold, further data did not significantly enhance the model's predictive capabilities, suggesting a bottleneck in model complexity or data quality. Moreover, investigating pretraining tasks revealed that combining masked language modelling with the prediction of physicochemical molecular descriptors outperformed masked language modeling alone and also models that were randomly initialised, particularly in low data regimes. However, the effort required for pretraining may not be justifiable when sufficient finetuning data is available.

Furthermore, the model exhibited varying degrees of accuracy across different reaction types, which is caused by a lack of information in the training data for some classes. This situation could likely be alleviated by incorporating information on the reaction conditions into forward reaction prediction. While there are classes of reactions that can be predicted with a 100% top-1 molecular accuracy, predictions for other classes range considerably lower than the average accuracy of 56%. These classes on which the model performs poorly tend to be classes where it is common that important reactants are missing from the data. This problem can be partially circumvented by providing the model with the information which reaction type is expected from a set of reactants. However, the predictions of such a model always need to be considered together with the predictions of a model that did not have this additional information to address challenges related to regioselectivity and especially chemoselectivity.

The models produce promising results regarding their intended use for the validation

of synthesis steps, as it performs well on reactions that are known to be challenging for retrosynthesis models. Its proficiency in these scenarios complements the existing capabilities of retrosynthesis tools, potentially helping to improve the quality of generated synthesis routes. Additionally, the model's potential to anticipate side reactions and foresee impurities provides valuable insights. By preemptively identifying these complexities, it aids chemists in devising more robust and efficient synthesis pathways while mitigating the impact of undesirable side and byproducts.

Despite its promising applications, the model has clear limitations, such as its inability to account for conservation of mass and stereochemistry, highlighting opportunities for future research. Investigating larger models with different architectures, integrating reaction conditions and yields into predictions, and incorporating chemical knowledge to enhance explainability and generalisability represent promising directions for advancing forward reaction prediction models. Availability of high quality data is of utmost importance for such schemes, but remains the biggest challenge.

In conclusion, while the current model offers valuable insights and complements existing retrosynthesis tools, future research endeavours should focus on addressing its limitations and exploring innovative approaches to enhance its performance and applicability in synthetic chemistry.

A Appendix

Figure A.1: A reaction from Reaxys, that is categorised as purification by NextMove. The SMILES strings for reactant and product are not identical, because the SMILES notation is not able to represent the aromaticity [99].

Figure A.2: Finetuning behaviour of models pretrained for 50 thousand, 6 million and 8 million steps on the MLM pretraining task. Finetuning on 5 million reactions.

Figure A.3: Finetuning on five million reactions for models pretrained with two different sequence representation strategies for descriptor prediction. Randomly initialised model for comparison.

Figure A.4: A reaction from Bruice [94], where two products are produced in equal measure. Target 1 is predicted with a Likelihood of 0.23 and Target 2 with a Likelihood of 0.05.

References

- [1] Philippe Schwaller and Teodoro Laino. "Data-driven learning systems for chemical reaction prediction: an analysis of recent approaches". In: *Machine Learning in Chemistry: Data-Driven Algorithms, Learning Systems, and Predictions*. ACS Publications, 2019, pp. 61–79.
- [2] Connor W Coley, William H Green, and Klavs F Jensen. "Machine learning in computer-aided synthesis planning". In: *Accounts of chemical research* 51.5 (2018), pp. 1281–1289.
- [3] Venkat Venkatasubramanian and Vipul Mann. "Artificial intelligence in reaction prediction and chemical synthesis". In: *Current Opinion in Chemical Engineering* 36 (2022), p. 100749.
- [4] Tomasz Badowski, Karol Molga, and Bartosz A Grzybowski. "Selection of cost-effective yet chemically diverse pathways from the networks of computer-generated retrosynthetic plans". In: *Chemical science* 10.17 (2019), pp. 4640–4651.
- [5] Alessandra Toniato et al. "Enhancing diversity in language based models for single-step retrosynthesis". In: *Digital Discovery* 2.2 (2023), pp. 489–501.
- [6] Philippe Schwaller et al. "Predicting retrosynthetic pathways using transformer-based models and a hyper-graph exploration strategy". In: *Chemical science* 11.12 (2020), pp. 3316–3325.
- [7] Peter Ertl et al. "Chemical Reactivity Prediction: Current Methods and Different Application Areas". In: *Molecular informatics* 41.6 (2022), p. 2100277.
- [8] Kjell Jorner et al. "Organic reactivity from mechanism to machine learning". In: *Nature Reviews Chemistry* 5.4 (2021), pp. 240–255.
- [9] Nadine Schneider et al. "Big data from pharmaceutical patents: a computational analysis of medicinal chemists' bread and butter". In: *Journal of medicinal chemistry* 59.9 (2016), pp. 4385–4402.
- [10] Keith T Butler et al. "Machine learning for molecular and materials science". In: *Nature* 559.7715 (2018), pp. 547–555.
- [11] Ashish Vaswani et al. "Attention is all you need". In: *Advances in neural information processing systems* 30 (2017).
- [12] Thomas Wolf et al. "Transformers: State-of-the-art natural language processing". In: *Proceedings of the 2020 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing: system demonstrations*. 2020, pp. 38–45.

- [13] Colin Raffel et al. “Exploring the limits of transfer learning with a unified text-to-text transformer”. In: *The Journal of Machine Learning Research* 21.1 (2020), pp. 5485–5551.
- [14] Kai Han et al. “A survey on vision transformer”. In: *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* 45.1 (2022), pp. 87–110.
- [15] Yanrong Ji et al. “DNABERT: pre-trained Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers model for DNA-language in genome”. In: *Bioinformatics* 37.15 (2021), pp. 2112–2120.
- [16] Yann LeCun, Yoshua Bengio, and Geoffrey Hinton. “Deep learning”. In: *nature* 521.7553 (2015), pp. 436–444.
- [17] Nathaniel Egwu, Thomas Mrziglod, and Andreas Schuppert. “Neural network input feature selection using structured l₂- norm penalization”. In: *Applied Intelligence* 53.5 (2023), pp. 5732–5749.
- [18] Charu C. Aggarwal. *Neural Networks and Deep Learning*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2018.
- [19] Kevin P. Murphy. *Probabilistic Machine Learning: An introduction*. MIT Press, 2022. URL: probml.ai.
- [20] Timothy P Lillicrap et al. “Backpropagation and the brain”. In: *Nature Reviews Neuroscience* 21.6 (2020), pp. 335–346.
- [21] Diederik P Kingma and Jimmy Ba. “Adam: A method for stochastic optimization”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6980* (2014).
- [22] Fengxiang He, Tongliang Liu, and Dacheng Tao. “Control batch size and learning rate to generalize well: Theoretical and empirical evidence”. In: *Advances in neural information processing systems* 32 (2019).
- [23] Rene Y Choi et al. “Introduction to machine learning, neural networks, and deep learning”. In: *Translational vision science & technology* 9.2 (2020), pp. 14–14.
- [24] Will Koehrsen. *Neural Network Embeddings Explained*. 2018. URL: <https://towardsdatascience.com/neural-network-embeddings-explained-4d028e6f0526>.
- [25] Markus Freitag and Yaser Al-Onaizan. “Beam search strategies for neural machine translation”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1702.01806* (2017).
- [26] Andrew Johnson. *Understanding Attention and Correlation in Transformers: A Deep Dive*. accessed 25 Feb 2024. 2023. URL: https://medium.com/@andrew_johnson_4/understanding-attention-and-correlation-in-transformers-a-deep-dive-4f190fc665fe.
- [27] Jay Alammr. *The Illustrated Transformer*. 2018. URL: <https://jalammr.github.io/illustrated-transformer/>.

- [28] Alec Radford et al. "Robust speech recognition via large-scale weak supervision". In: *International Conference on Machine Learning*. PMLR. 2023, pp. 28492–28518.
- [29] John Jumper et al. "Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold". In: *Nature* 596.7873 (2021), pp. 583–589.
- [30] Philippe Schwaller et al. "Molecular transformer: a model for uncertainty-calibrated chemical reaction prediction". In: *ACS central science* 5.9 (2019), pp. 1572–1583.
- [31] Elias James Corey. "General methods for the construction of complex molecules". In: *Pure and Applied chemistry* 14.1 (1967), pp. 19–38.
- [32] Wendy A Warr. "A short review of chemical reaction database systems, computer-aided synthesis design, reaction prediction and synthetic feasibility". In: *Molecular Informatics* 33.6-7 (2014), pp. 469–476.
- [33] Bartosz A Grzybowski et al. "Network search algorithms and scoring functions for advanced-level computerized synthesis planning". In: *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Molecular Science* 13.1 (2023), e1630.
- [34] Philippe Schwaller et al. "Machine intelligence for chemical reaction space". In: *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Molecular Science* 12.5 (2022), e1604.
- [35] Connor W Coley et al. "Prediction of organic reaction outcomes using machine learning". In: *ACS central science* 3.5 (2017), pp. 434–443.
- [36] Francisco J Montáns et al. "Data-driven modeling and learning in science and engineering". In: *Comptes Rendus Mécanique* 347.11 (2019), pp. 845–855.
- [37] Wengong Jin et al. "Predicting Organic Reaction Outcomes with Weisfeiler-Lehman Network". In: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*. Ed. by I. Guyon et al. Vol. 30. Curran Associates, Inc., 2017. URL: https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2017/file/ced556cd9f9c0c8315cfbe0744a3baf0-Paper.pdf.
- [38] Philippe Schwaller et al. "'Found in Translation': predicting outcomes of complex organic chemistry reactions using neural sequence-to-sequence models". In: *Chemical science* 9.28 (2018), pp. 6091–6098.
- [39] Richard Apodaca et al. *OpenSMILES specification*. 2007. URL: www.opensmiles.org.
- [40] Noel M O'Boyle. "Towards a Universal SMILES representation-A standard method to generate canonical SMILES based on the InChI". In: *Journal of cheminformatics* 4 (2012), pp. 1–14.
- [41] Elsevier Limited. *Reaxys*. accessed Nov 29 2023. URL: <https://www.reaxys.com/#/search/quick>.
- [42] CAS. *CAS reactions*. accessed Nov 29 2023. URL: <https://www.cas.org/cas-data/cas-reactions>.

- [43] Steven M Kearnes et al. "The open reaction database". In: *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 143.45 (2021), pp. 18820–18826.
- [44] Steven Y Feng et al. "A survey of data augmentation approaches for NLP". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2105.03075* (2021).
- [45] Igor V Tetko et al. "State-of-the-art augmented NLP transformer models for direct and single-step retrosynthesis". In: *Nature communications* 11.1 (2020), p. 5575.
- [46] Marwin HS Segler, Mike Preuss, and Mark P Waller. "Planning chemical syntheses with deep neural networks and symbolic AI". In: *Nature* 555.7698 (2018), pp. 604–610.
- [47] Miriam Wollenhaupt, Martin Villalba, and Orr Ravitz. *Predicting New Chemistry - Impact of High-Quality Training Data on Prediction of Reaction Outcomes*. accessed Feb 13 2024. URL: https://www.cas.org/sites/default/files/documents/%7Bf8e82e3b-f3e5-4b40-8567-ad05e555a397%7D_CASGENENGWHP100045210427-Predicting-New-Chemistry-White-Paper.pdf.
- [48] Felix Strieth-Kalthoff et al. "Machine learning for chemical reactivity: The importance of failed experiments". In: *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 61.29 (2022), e202204647.
- [49] Juno Nam and Jurae Kim. "Linking the neural machine translation and the prediction of organic chemistry reactions". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1612.09529* (2016).
- [50] Umit V Ucak, Islambek Ashyrmamatov, and Juyong Lee. "Improving the quality of chemical language model outcomes with atom-in-SMILES tokenization". In: *Journal of Cheminformatics* 15.1 (2023), p. 55.
- [51] G Skoraczyński et al. "Predicting the outcomes of organic reactions via machine learning: are current descriptors sufficient?" In: *Scientific reports* 7.1 (2017), p. 3582.
- [52] Ross Irwin et al. "Chemformer: a pre-trained transformer for computational chemistry". In: *Machine Learning: Science and Technology* 3.1 (2022), p. 015022.
- [53] Lisa Torrey and Jude Shavlik. "Transfer learning". In: *Handbook of research on machine learning applications and trends: algorithms, methods, and techniques*. IGI global, 2010, pp. 242–264.
- [54] Koustuv Sinha et al. "Masked language modeling and the distributional hypothesis: Order word matters pre-training for little". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2104.06644* (2021).
- [55] Jerret Ross et al. "Large-scale chemical language representations capture molecular structure and properties". In: *Nature Machine Intelligence* 4.12 (2022), pp. 1256–1264.

- [56] Teague Sterling and John J Irwin. "ZINC 15–ligand discovery for everyone". In: *Journal of chemical information and modeling* 55.11 (2015), pp. 2324–2337.
- [57] Sunghwan Kim et al. "PubChem 2019 update: improved access to chemical data". In: *Nucleic acids research* 47.D1 (2019), pp. D1102–D1109.
- [58] Benedek Fabian et al. "Molecular representation learning with language models and domain-relevant auxiliary tasks". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2011.13230* (2020).
- [59] RDKit. *Open-source cheminformatics*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10275225>. URL: <https://www.rdkit.org>.
- [60] Annie M Westerlund et al. "Do Chemformers dream of organic matter? Evaluating a transformer model for multi-step retrosynthesis". In: *ChemRxiv. Cambridge: Cambridge Open Engage* (2023).
- [61] Mike Lewis et al. "Bart: Denoising sequence-to-sequence pre-training for natural language generation, translation, and comprehension". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1910.13461* (2019).
- [62] Jacob Devlin et al. "Bert: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.04805* (2018).
- [63] PyTorch Contributors. *Transformer*. accessed 12 Feb 2024. 2023. URL: <https://pytorch.org/docs/stable/generated/torch.nn.Transformer.html#torch.nn.Transformer>.
- [64] Qian Chen, Zhen-Hua Ling, and Xiaodan Zhu. "Enhancing sentence embedding with generalized pooling". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1806.09828* (2018).
- [65] Imrus Salehin and Dae-Ki Kang. "A review on dropout regularization approaches for deep neural networks within the scholarly domain". In: *Electronics* 12.14 (2023), p. 3106.
- [66] Adam Paszke et al. "Pytorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library". In: *Advances in neural information processing systems* 32 (2019).
- [67] William Falcon and The PyTorch Lightning team. *PyTorch Lightning*. Version 1.4. Mar. 2019. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3828935. URL: <https://github.com/Lightning-AI/lightning>.
- [68] Michael Gschwind, Driss Guessous, and Christian Puhersch. *Accelerated PyTorch 2 Transformers*. 2023. URL: <https://pytorch.org/blog/accelerated-pytorch-2/>.
- [69] Esben Bjerrum et al. "PySMILESUtils–enabling deep learning with the SMILES chemical language". In: (2021).
- [70] Sam Wiseman and Alexander M Rush. "Sequence-to-sequence learning as beam-search optimization". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1606.02960* (2016).

- [71] Dassault Systèmes. *BIOVIA Pipeline Pilot*. accessed Jan 06 2024. URL: <https://www.3ds.com/products/biovia/pipeline-pilot>.
- [72] Scott A Wildman and Gordon M Crippen. "Prediction of physicochemical parameters by atomic contributions". In: *Journal of chemical information and computer sciences* 39.5 (1999), pp. 868–873.
- [73] Peter Ertl, Bernhard Rohde, and Paul Selzer. "Fast calculation of molecular polar surface area as a sum of fragment-based contributions and its application to the prediction of drug transport properties". In: *Journal of medicinal chemistry* 43.20 (2000), pp. 3714–3717.
- [74] Harry L Morgan. "The generation of a unique machine description for chemical structures—a technique developed at chemical abstracts service." In: *Journal of chemical documentation* 5.2 (1965), pp. 107–113.
- [75] Angelos Katharopoulos et al. "Transformers are rnns: Fast autoregressive transformers with linear attention". In: *International conference on machine learning*. PMLR. 2020, pp. 5156–5165.
- [76] NextMove Software. *NameRxn - Expert System for Named Reaction Identification and Classification*. accessed Jan 08 2024. URL: <https://www.nextmovesoftware.com/namerxn.html>.
- [77] John S Carey et al. "Analysis of the reactions used for the preparation of drug candidate molecules". In: *Organic & biomolecular chemistry* 4.12 (2006), pp. 2337–2347.
- [78] Stephen D Roughley and Allan M Jordan. "The medicinal chemist's toolbox: an analysis of reactions used in the pursuit of drug candidates". In: *Journal of medicinal chemistry* 54.10 (2011), pp. 3451–3479.
- [79] F. Pedregosa et al. "Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in Python". In: *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 12 (2011), pp. 2825–2830.
- [80] In-Kwon Yeo and Richard A. Johnson. "A new family of power transformations to improve normality or symmetry". In: *Biometrika* 87.4 (Dec. 2000), pp. 954–959. ISSN: 0006-3444. DOI: 10.1093/biomet/87.4.954. eprint: <https://academic.oup.com/biomet/article-pdf/87/4/954/633221/870954.pdf>. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1093/biomet/87.4.954>.
- [81] Xavier Glorot and Yoshua Bengio. "Understanding the difficulty of training deep feedforward neural networks". In: *Proceedings of the thirteenth international conference on artificial intelligence and statistics*. JMLR Workshop and Conference Proceedings. 2010, pp. 249–256.

- [82] Yang You et al. "Large batch optimization for deep learning: Training bert in 76 minutes". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.00962* (2019).
- [83] Sebastian Ruder. "An overview of gradient descent optimization algorithms". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1609.04747* (2016).
- [84] PyTorch Contributors. *Reproducibility*. accessed 11 Jan 2024. 2023. URL: <https://pytorch.org/docs/stable/notes/randomness.html>.
- [85] Paula Torren-Peraire et al. "Models Matter: The Impact of Single-Step Retrosynthesis on Synthesis Planning". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2308.05522* (2023).
- [86] Rishi Bommasani et al. "On the opportunities and risks of foundation models". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.07258* (2021).
- [87] Maria H Rasmussen, Diana S Christensen, and Jan H Jensen. "Do machines dream of atoms? Crippen's logP as a quantitative molecular benchmark for explainable AI heatmaps". In: *SciPost Chemistry* 2.1 (2023), p. 002.
- [88] Priyanka Chaudhary et al. "Regioselective nitration of N-alkyl anilines using tert-butyl nitrite under mild condition". In: *The Journal of Organic Chemistry* 84.1 (2018), pp. 104–119.
- [89] Stefano Marcaccini and Tomás Torroba. "The use of the Ugi four-component condensation". In: *Nature Protocols* 2.3 (2007), pp. 632–639.
- [90] Paul Jaccard. "The distribution of the flora in the alpine zone. 1". In: *New phytologist* 11.2 (1912), pp. 37–50.
- [91] David J Rogers and Taffee T Tanimoto. "A Computer Program for Classifying Plants: The computer is programmed to simulate the taxonomic process of comparing each case with every other case." In: *Science* 132.3434 (1960), pp. 1115–1118.
- [92] Roberto Todeschini et al. "Similarity coefficients for binary chemoinformatics data: overview and extended comparison using simulated and real data sets". In: *Journal of chemical information and modeling* 52.11 (2012), pp. 2884–2901.
- [93] Will Watson. *On byproducts and side products*. 2012.
- [94] Paula Yurkanis Bruice. *Organic chemistry*. Pearson, 2017.
- [95] Jonathan Clayden, Nick Greeves, and Stuart Warren. *Organic chemistry*. Oxford University Press, USA, 2012.
- [96] Barry M Trost and Ian Fleming. *Comprehensive organic synthesis: selectivity, strategy, and efficiency in modern organic chemistry*. Vol. 8. Elsevier, 1991.
- [97] Yingchao Yan et al. "RPBP: Deep Retrosynthesis Reaction Prediction Based on Byproducts". In: *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling* 63.19 (2023), pp. 5956–5970.

- [98] Roweida Mohammed, Jumanah Rawashdeh, and Malak Abdullah. "Machine learning with oversampling and undersampling techniques: overview study and experimental results". In: *2020 11th international conference on information and communication systems (ICICS)*. IEEE. 2020, pp. 243–248.
- [99] Josef Scharf et al. "Stereochemie planar chiraler Verbindungen, 10. Mitt.: Röntgenkristallstruktur und absolute Chiralität überbrückter [10]-und [14] Anulene: X-ray crystal structures and absolute chiralities of bridged [10]-and [14] anulenes". In: *Monatshefte für Chemie/Chemical Monthly* 117 (1986), pp. 255–267.